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The transition from below: Aspirations, problems and policy solutions across the globe

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Abstract

Nation states, regions and communities across the globe experience “losses and damages to nature and people”, but those “who have historically contributed the least to current climate change are disproportionately affected [...]” (IPCC, 2023:5). This report addresses how governments – from the perspective of different interest groups and citizens – should balance efforts to tackle ecological challenges, including climate change, with economic and social priorities. Adopting a cross-national comparative case study approach, we investigate citizens’ perspectives on sustainability transitions in seven countries – Hungary, Italy, Kenya, the Netherlands, Norway, Pakistan and Sri Lanka – located in different global regions. We study similarities and differences in relation to citizens’ aspirations, perceived problems and ideas about transition policy.

A key contribution of the study is the use of an open-source world-building tabletop game, Le Grand Jeu, to elicit the perspectives of citizens in widely different settings. Research teams in the selected countries organised workshops where the participants were invited to play a customised version of the Le Grand Jeu, followed by a more structured group discussions.

The findings suggest that that the vision of sustainability is an uncontroversial and shared objective across Europe and the Global South. The satisfaction of basic needs and a reduction of social inequalities stood out as defining features of sustainable human development and must underpin policies for ecological sustainability. The lack of opportunities for citizen participation and empowerment was perceived as a shortcoming in the development of policies for sustainability in Europe as well as in the Global South countries. Overall, citizens’ perspectives are shaped by contextual and structural factors, like the level of social and economic development, institutional and government capacity, and ecological vulnerabilities, leading to variation in the policy issues that stand at the forefront of national and local sustainability transition agendas. The Global South countries placed a stronger emphasis on economic development and the improvement of material living standards, while the issue of overconsumption featured more prominently in the European countries.

1. Introduction

In devising policy for the sustainability transition, it is paramount to consider the perceived as well as actual consequences across different groups of the population with different characteristics – within and across countries. Adverse effects of human-induced climate change are no local phenomena. We know that across the globe communities experience “losses and damages to nature and people”, but importantly, those “who have historically contributed the least to current climate change are disproportionately affected (high confidence)” (IPCC, 2023: 5). This report addresses how governments – from the perspective of different interest groups and citizens – should balance efforts to tackle ecological challenges, including climate change, with other economic and social priorities. We are interested in what they highlight as the common aspirations, challenges and main policy ideas. We study similarities and differences in this regard across a selection of European and Global South countries.

A key contribution of the study is the use of an innovative method for collecting qualitative data. Research teams in four European and three Global South countries organised workshops where the participants were invited to *play Le Grand Jeu (LGJ)*, an open-source world-building tabletop game customized for the purposes of the Horizon Europe funded SPES project, which aims to improve our knowledge and understanding of the interconnections between economic growth, human flourishing, and sustainability (see Biggeri et al., 2023). The project brings together the objectives of equity, productivity, environmental sustainability, participation and empowerment, and human security as a basis for sustainable human development (see Section 6 for an elaboration and discussion).

Image 1: Workshops in Sri Lanka

Our game-based workshop approach provided a stimulating, interactive, and safe environment within which the participants, regardless of their expertise, were prompted to develop sustainability transition scenarios for an imaginary society facing real-world problems, and to collectively identify and discuss the associated challenges and opportunities. The participating countries were Hungary, Italy, Kenya, the Netherlands, Norway, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka, selected to capture a broad range of geographic regions, socio-economic contexts, and sustainability challenges.

The countries included in the study differ greatly on a long list of important dimensions, ranging from demographic and economic structures via politics and institutional capacity to energy systems and climatic conditions. Hence, there are significant contrasts in the social, environmental and economic problems and policy priorities on the political agenda in these countries (Schoyen et al., 2023). Nevertheless, they have in common that they face the challenge of climate change and the need to promote a fair transition towards ecologically safe and socially inclusive societies. The principle of common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities, which underpins international climate negotiations, recognises the shared and borderless implications of the climate emergency. In low-, middle- and high-income countries alike, this acknowledgement requires changes to public policy across a wide range of policy fields. Therefore, we follow Zens et al. (2025: 5) in acknowledging that there is “a need to understand sustainability challenges across

diverse development contexts, recognizing that transition pathways must be adapted to local conditions while addressing global imperatives.” This study offers a further contribution to this end.

Moreover, our study is motivated by sustainability science’s call for broad collaboration through stakeholder and citizen participation in research and knowledge creation about and for sustainability transitions (see Berti Suman et al., 2023). We draw inspiration from an influential piece by Kates et al. (2001: 641), who argue that “in a world put at risk by the unintended consequences of scientific progress, participatory procedures involving scientists, stakeholders, advocates, active citizens, and users of knowledge are critically needed.” Such collaborations have several potential benefits, for instance, through improved legitimacy and ownership to problem definitions and policy solutions, which in this way may also become more feasible (Huttunen et al., 2022; Lang et al., 2012). Focusing more narrowly on the involvement of citizens in transitions research, Huttunen et al. (2022: 2) identifies four types of engagement: “(1) envisioning sustainable futures; (2) implementing local transitions; (3) revealing public perceptions; and (4) developing participatory methods.” Our study aligns with three of these purposes. Only the implementation of local transitions was beyond the scope of the SPES project.

The report proceeds in six further main sections. Section 2 offers a brief discussion of different methodological approaches to the study of citizens’ perspectives on sustainability transitions. We make a case for the benefits of qualitative, participatory approaches to complement traditional survey data of popular attitudes. In Section 3 we move to the empirical context of the country cases included in this study, to understand better the backdrop for the themes, questions and opinions that emerged during the workshops and interviews carried out in the seven countries. While it is not feasible to provide a full account of the structural, political, economic and social characteristics of these countries, the purpose is to illustrate, taking a bird’s eye view, how the everyday challenges decisionmakers and citizens face, differ considerably across the globe. We do this with the help of a few macro indicators and a brief description of the ‘socio-ecological’ profiles of the included countries. These differences will influence citizens’ views on sustainability transitions in relation to their aspirations, perceived problems and ideas about transition policy. Section 4 turns to a description of the empirical research carried out in each of the countries, including how the workshops were adapted in each country case. Section 5 presents the main empirical results from the participatory workshops and in some cases interviews, before we analyse the findings in a comparative perspective in Section 6. In doing so, we draw on selected parts of the SPES framework for sustainable human development. Section 7 summarises and concludes. As part of this final exercise, we also offer a set of broad policy recommendations.

2. Citizens' perspectives on sustainability transitions: Research approaches

As noted above, climate change both affects and demands policy action from countries in the Global South and the Global North. The low-income countries of the Global South bear little responsibility for global warming, since, historically, they are very modest emitters of greenhouse gases. Yet, facing the strongest and most negative impacts of global warming, climate adaptation efforts are pressing (Fankhauser, 1994; Tol, 2018, 2021). More specifically, countries in the Global South are more susceptible to harmful consequences of climate change due to the continued importance of water and climate-sensitive sectors like agriculture like in many economies. Furthermore, compared with many affluent economies, countries in the Global South typically have less capacity for adaptive action, associated in part with shortcomings in the capacity of government (Adger, 2006). Therefore, for “developing countries” the “best defense against climate change may be their own continued development” (Schelling, 1992: 6), which would improve their capacities to tackle climate impacts.

For Europe and other countries in the Global North the story is different. While they are far from immune to negative physical and human consequences of climate change, they benefit from higher levels of human and economic capital and better technological and bureaucratic capacities than in the Global South (see below). These factors facilitate the ability to attract necessary investments and undertake adaptation measures to reduce vulnerabilities to current and future expected adverse climate impacts in Global North countries.

While governments across the world are required to react to the climate emergency, in doing so they need to consider that policy does not have an even impact across populations. Factors that may interact to affect individual policy consequences include demographic and socio-economic characteristics like education, income, profession, gender, marital status, ethnicity, and place of residence. Such variation may lead to differences in policy preferences and in the degree of public acceptance of different policy solutions. As Dokken et al. (2025: 6) argue the “(lack of) public acceptance of transition policies impacts the scope for politicians to enact public policies that facilitate sustainability transitions”. Decision-makers are aware that citizens' perceptions and attitudes influence how they vote in elections. Thus, their beliefs about popular attitudes may shape the policy agenda in an enabling or constraining direction (Cooper and Burchardt, 2022).

At the same time, research has found that decision-makers are not always good at assessing public support for or against a policy. For instance, a study by Walgrave et al. (2022) show that politicians are rather inaccurate in their estimates of what citizens want, knowledge that is essential to produce policies that are responsive to citizens' needs and preferences. Moreover, opinion surveys consist of questions imposing on the respondents a top-down framing of the questions raised. In this way “the preconceptions of researchers [or the survey designers] shape and frame the way in which attitudes are addressed and measured, casting emphasis on some issues and downplaying or ignoring others” (Chung et al., 2018: 843). If the survey framing is at odds with the respondents' actual understanding of the issues and opinions the survey claims to measure, citizens' actual attitudes might not be adequately captured. Hence, to mitigate this risk and more fully grasp citizens' perspectives on ‘wicked problems’ (Rittel and Webber, 1973) such as climate change and sustainability transitions, it is useful to complement tightly structured research methods with more open participatory approaches.

The overarching aim of the present study is, therefore, to explore and analyse how individuals and communities conceptualise sustainability, identify systemic challenges, and (co-)imagine policy pathways towards sustainable and equitable futures. Drawing on selected concepts from the SPES project's analytical framework on sustainability transitions (Biggeri et al., 2023, 2025), we employed a combination of participatory and conventional qualitative methods. At the core our approach were workshops in which participants played the play *Le Grand Jeu (LGJ)* (Bonelli and Rovida, 2016; Petz et al., 2024; Sauer and Bonelli, 2020), which we customised to the research needs of the SPES project. With some national variations, the participants selected their own roles and were encouraged to develop a transition scenario through interaction with other players. This allowed them to explore sustainability dilemmas creatively in an engaging setting. As a research tool, the objective was to trigger dynamic decision-making, reflections and natural conversations which would shed light on the general public's and different sub-groups' "framing of ideas" (Taylor-Gooby et al., 2018), underpinning participants' imaginaries, problem perceptions and envisioned policy solutions. The game was designed to surface tensions between individual and collective goals and to provide an opportunity to observe how people negotiate trade-offs and seek solutions in a focus group-like setting.

The research design process was another important feature of the study. It was a collaborative effort involving researchers from the seven countries listed above. This diversity of regional and national contexts enabled us to explore how perspectives on sustainability vary across different institutional, economic, and cultural settings. Importantly, local partners had the freedom to adapt the research design to their specific contexts, ensuring sensitivity to differing socio-cultural and economic conditions and enhancing the relevance for and responsiveness to participants.

Le Grand Jeu (LGJ) is an example of a 'serious game'. These kinds of games have been widely applied across various contexts to serve diverse purposes, demonstrating their versatility as tools for engagement, learning, and decision-making. In educational settings, serious games are primarily used to enhance learning outcomes by immersing participants in interactive and experiential environments. They facilitate cognitive, social, and experiential learning by allowing players to simulate complex systems, explore abstract concepts, and develop skills such as negotiation, collaboration, and critical thinking (Blokland et al., 2021; Gugerell, 2023; Speelman et al., 2023). This makes them particularly useful in fields like sustainability education, where they help learners understand the interdependencies of social, environmental, and economic systems.

In the realm of policy development, serious games are often employed to explore and test potential solutions to societal challenges. By simulating decision-making scenarios and enabling stakeholders to experience the outcomes of their choices in a risk-free environment, these games promote the co-creation of policies and strategies (Vesnic-Alujevic and Rosa, 2022). They are particularly valuable for addressing wicked problems, such as climate change and resource management, as they foster dialogue among diverse actors while flattening hierarchies, reveal trade-offs, and encourage innovation (Salliou et al., 2021; Speelman et al., 2023). Policymakers can use insights from these games to better understand public reactions to proposed measures and refine strategies accordingly. In a research setting, serious games may be used as an alternative to traditional focus groups as a method to collect qualitative data. By immersing participants in scenario-based gameplay, they can articulate their values and priorities in a setting that simulates real-world dynamics. The debriefing sessions that follow are critical for extracting rich qualitative data, as they encourage participants to reflect on their experiences and connect them to broader societal issues (Gugerell, 2023; Kriz, 2010) This application is particularly relevant in participatory research contexts, where serious games serve as boundary objects that facilitate understanding and collaboration among diverse stakeholders (Salliou et al., 2021).

In our case, beyond serving as a method for exploring perceptions and trade-offs around sustainability, we also viewed the serious game workshops as sites of bottom-up democratic

experimentation. They were designed to elicit locally grounded policy solutions from participants, including laypersons who often do not feel empowered to express their preferences or are not routinely heard in formal consultation processes. For this reason, this kind of workshops can be understood not only as research instruments, but as participatory democratic supplements to representative electoral systems, which are increasingly under strain (Van Reybrouck et al., 2014). Across the globe, liberal democracies face a legitimacy crisis marked by growing political disaffection, declining trust in elected representatives, and a resurgence of authoritarian governance (Matlosa, 2023; Prats et al., 2024; Valgarðsson et al., 2025).

3. Human and planetary wellbeing around the globe

Everyone, as a member of society, has the right to social security and is entitled to realization, through national effort and international co-operation and in accordance with the organization and resources of each State, of the economic, social and cultural rights indispensable for his dignity and the free development of his personality (United Nations, 1948).

Article 22 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) provides all human beings with the right to social security along with the social and economic rights necessary to live in dignity. Taking a bird's eye view of the world and our selected country cases, a selection of macro indicators commonly used to assess different dimensions of sustainability provides us with a simple but stark picture of global inequalities. Overall, these indicators demonstrate that where you live matters a great deal for the prospects of enjoying adequate living standards and a safe and healthy environment.

Figure 1 compares results for the seven countries cases and the world, relying on the Human Development Index (HDI) and two associated composite human development indices – Inequality adjusted HDI (IHDI), and Planetary-pressure adjusted HDI (PHDI). In addition, we display the Sustainable Development Index (SDI) scores. The first three indices are among the statistical tables calculated for the annual Human Development Report (HDR), the flagship publication of the United Nation Human Development Programme. The SDI has been developed by Hickel in an effort to better account for the ecological impact of human development (Hickel, 2020). A novelty of the SDI is that it places a sufficiency threshold on per capita income threshold, above which any additional income does not improve a country's SDI score. The method reflects a strong sustainability approach that does not permit high levels of human development as a compensation for weak ecological performance and vice versa.

Norway is consistently among the top three nations in the HDI ranking. In the 2025 HDR Norway shares the second place with Switzerland, only after Iceland. Also, the Netherlands achieves a place among the top ten. Italy and Hungary, ranked 29th and 46th respectively, are a little further down the list but still classified as countries with very high human development. In contrast, ranked 168 of 193 countries, Pakistan belongs to the countries with low human development. Ranked 143rd, Kenya enjoys a medium level of human development while Sri Lanka in 89th position has a high level of human development.

The IHDI captures inequalities in the distribution across the population of each component indicator. The HDI and IHDI values are equal when there is no inequality, but the latter drops as inequality increases. As shown in Figure 1, inequality – indicated by the gap between the HDI and IHDI values – is greater in the countries with a lower level of human development. The pattern is similar for gender inequality as women tend to face a higher degree of disadvantage compared with men in the less developed regions (not shown in Figure 1, but see table 5 in UNDP, 2025a), reinforcing the level of societal challenges poorer nations face.

However, when incorporating environmental dimension in assessments of development, the comparative picture changes. The UNDP also calculates a PHDI. This measure follows the same logic as the IHDI but instead of focusing on inequality, the PHDI incorporates an ecological

dimension in the measure of human development. The greater the environmental pressure a country's activities put on the planet (measured as per capita material footprint and CO₂ emissions), the further the PHDI falls below the HDI (UNDP, 2025b). From Figure 1 it is evident that rich countries like Norway and the Netherlands have societies that exert a high pressure on the environment compared with the three Global South countries included among our cases. The SDI does not award per capita income in the same way as the HDI and penalises more severely the degree of ecological impact. Consequently, particularly Norway but also the Netherlands trail far below the other countries in this study. By contrast, according to the SDI approach, Sri Lanka emerges as a top performer, with third place according to the 2024 data. In fact, Hickel praises Sri Lanka for investing "heavily in public healthcare and education, [showing] that it is possible for poorer countries to dramatically improve their social outcomes without needing ecologically destructive levels of economic activity to do so" (Hickel, 2020: 8–9).

Figure 1: Taking stock of human development and sustainability in seven countries

Note: While the HDI, IHDI and PHDI are reported for 2023, the SDI values apply to 2022. The countries are sorted in descending order on the HDI scores.

Source: United Nations Development Programme (2025a), University of Notre Dame (2025) and SDI project (SDI project, 2024)

Another useful metric is the ND-GAIN country index which is a composite of two main dimensions: vulnerability to climate hazards and readiness to adapt (ND-GAIN, 2024). Figure 2 displays what is called the ND-GAIN matrix, highlighting the seven case countries in this study. The matrix illustrates well that the most vulnerable countries also display a low level of adaptation readiness, implying *inter alia* a poor capacity to attract and a weak ability to leverage investments in adaptation actions. Conversely, countries in affluent parts of the world, e.g., in Europe, tend to be less vulnerable and well positioned to undertake adaptation measures.

Figure 2: ND-GAIN matrix, 2023

Source: replication of the ND-GAIN matrix, University of Notre Dame (2025)

The final factor that we consider in this broad-brush comparison of the context in which the sustainability transition will unfold, is differences in economic structure. The extent to which workers feel the physical consequences of climate change or are affected by climate mitigation policy depends on the type of sectoral affiliation. While acknowledging that there is a lot of variation within these broad sectors, we can say that primary sector workers, in, for instance, agriculture, have livelihoods that are more weather dependent and, therefore, more susceptible to losses from climatic events like heatwaves or extreme rain (Abeysekara et al., 2023; Feriga et al., 2024). Similarly, workers engaged in energy-intensive industries such as construction and manufacturing will be particularly affected by measures to cut greenhouse gas emissions as part of the green transition (Abeysekara et al., 2023; Chateau et al., 2023; OECD, 2015). The increase in service sector employment is expected to continue to increase, but it should also be noted that there are large variations in the effects of climate change and climate policy when it comes to the service sector (OECD, 2015). Transport and tourism are examples of services that are highly exposed to climate risks as well as green transition efforts with the use of carbon pricing and new low-carbon transport solutions (Feriga et al., 2024).

Figure 3 helps us compare employment structures in our case countries and in the EU. It illustrates that service-sector employment dominates in European economies, particularly in Norway and the Netherlands. Since year 2000, employment in agriculture and industry has declined further. We observe the same trend in Kenya, Pakistan and Sri Lanka. However, employment in the primary sector continues to play a much larger role than in the rich European economies. Both Hungary and Italy still have relatively large shares of industrial employment and will see many workers affected by climate mitigation efforts which target this sector.

Figure 3: Employment structures compared

Note: The charts show employment in each sector as a percentage of total employment in the country.

Source: (World Bank, 2025d)

3.1. Global South country profiles

Building on the previous subsection’s global comparison of the case countries using indicators such as the HDI, SDI, PHDI, and IHDI, this section offers a more detailed examination of the national contexts. It provides in-depth insights into the demographic, economic, social, and political conditions that shape each country’s vulnerability to climate change and their capacity to adapt and contribute to global mitigation efforts.

3.1.1. Kenya

Kenya is located in East Africa, bordered by the Indian Ocean and traversed by the Great Rift Valley, featuring varied landscapes from highlands to savannahs and arid zones. The country gained independence from British colonial rule in 1963 and has since functioned as a unitary presidential republic. The 2010 Constitution introduced significant reforms, most notably the devolution of power to 47 county governments to promote democratic participation and more equitable regional development (Kanyinga, 2016; Omine and Ingham, 2025).

Demography

In 2025, Kenya’s population stands at approximately 53.3 million, with a median age of 25, making it one of the youngest populations globally. Youth aged 18–35 constitute around 75 per cent of the population, and nearly 40 per cent are under 15 (Kenya National Bureau of Statistics, 2019). Fertility rates have declined to 3.1 children per woman, yet population growth continues to strain infrastructure, services, and environmental resources. Life expectancy is estimated at 64 years—66.3 for women and 61 for men.

Kenya is ethnically diverse, comprising over 40 ethnic groups, including the Kikuyu, Luhya, Luo, Kalenjin, Kamba, and Kisii, along with smaller groups like the Mijikenda and Maasai. The official languages are English and Kiswahili, while numerous indigenous languages are spoken locally. Religiously, the population is predominantly Christian (Protestant and Roman Catholic), with a significant Muslim minority concentrated along the coast and smaller communities practicing traditional African religions or Hinduism (Wangila, 2023).

Economy

Kenya recorded a GDP growth rate of 4.0 per cent in 2024, indicating a modest recovery amid structural and fiscal challenges (KNBS, 2025). The economy remains heavily reliant on small-scale agriculture, which employs over 40 per cent of the total population and more than 70 per cent of the rural workforce. While the services sector—including tourism and horticulture—has gained importance, industrialization and formal employment remain limited (GoK, 2025; World Bank, 2025a).

Although the government supports industrialization through credit and manufacturing policies, the sector’s employment contribution remains modest, mainly limited to labour-intensive export

industries such as textiles, uncut flowers, and tourism (KNBS, 2025). Post-2022 employment rates have remained low despite growth in services (Janssens et al., 2021).

The informal sector, locally known as *hustling*, accounts for roughly three-quarters of all employment (Eichsteller et al., 2022; Murunga et al., 2021). It includes small-scale enterprises like shops, vegetable stalls, and motorcycle taxis (*boda bodas*), and is marked by low income, job insecurity, and lack of social protection. Women are particularly overrepresented in precarious and informal work (Riisgaard et al., 2024).

The state's fiscal space has been constrained by a rising debt-to-GDP ratio, with recent debt maturities prompting austerity measures and reductions in public and social services (Chome and Willis, 2024). Consequently, many households face high out-of-pocket costs for essential services like health and education. Kenya's social protection systems are insufficient and underfunded, offering limited support to vulnerable populations (Ouma, 2021). Poverty and inequality remain pressing concerns. Despite government poverty alleviation initiatives, well-being indicators have declined, particularly after COVID-19 (Oleche et al., 2023; Onyango, 2024).

Welfare

Kenya's welfare state is characterized by a rapidly evolving but still limited social protection system. While the government has expanded coverage through initiatives like the Inua Jamii cash transfer program and the National Health Insurance Fund (NHIF), overall public spending on social protection remains relatively low. The system is fragmented across multiple ministries and programs, leading to inefficiencies and coverage gaps. Fiscal constraints and weak coordination continue to limit the scalability and effectiveness of welfare initiatives, especially for vulnerable groups in informal employment and rural areas (World Bank, 2025a).

Political landscape

Kenya is a relatively young multiparty democracy but continues to face challenges in consolidating democratic institutions. Scoring 5.05 on the Democracy Index, it is classified as a "hybrid regime," marked by persistent issues such as electoral irregularities, corruption, and weak rule of law. While the 2010 Constitution strengthened devolution and representative frameworks, political competition remains highly centralized and often polarized along ethnic lines, constraining inclusive participation.

Climate vulnerability

Kenya is increasingly exposed to climate extremes, including prolonged droughts and severe flooding, which have had substantial impacts on agriculture, infrastructure, and energy systems (Asokan et al., 2025; Rotich et al., 2024). Climate variability, including fluctuating rainfall patterns and rising temperatures, has disrupted seasonal cycles and amplified socioeconomic risks. Sectors such as agriculture, tourism, energy, water, and health—on which many households rely—are especially vulnerable (World Bank Group, 2023).

Floods have caused displacement, infrastructure damage, and increased waterborne disease, often escalating into humanitarian crises. Pastoralist and semi-arid regions are particularly affected by El Niño–La Niña cycles that trigger alternating droughts and floods, undermining livelihoods and aggravating food insecurity. These conditions have also intensified competition over natural resources, resulting in migration and intercommunal conflict (Bedasa and Deksisa, 2024; Leal Filho et al., 2023).

Urban areas, especially informal settlements, are highly exposed to flood risks due to poor infrastructure and rapid population growth. At the same time, climate change has disrupted ecosystems and reduced productivity in crops, fisheries, and livestock, heightening vulnerability in both rural and urban settings (Bedasa and Deksisa, 2024).

Climate policy and governance

Kenya's Vision 2030 lays out a long-term agenda for sustainable, climate-resilient development, aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals. The 2016 National Climate Change Act established a legal framework for climate adaptation and mitigation (GoK, 2016), followed by key instruments such as the Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA) Strategy 2017–2026 and the Climate Finance Law 2017 (Ouma, 2023). The County Climate Change Fund and the Financing Locally Led Climate Action (FLLOCA) Programme operationalize resilience investments at the local level. Many of these policies are agriculture-focused, given the sector's centrality to livelihoods and vulnerability to climate impacts.

3.1.2. Pakistan

Pakistan, located in South Asia, shares borders with India, Afghanistan, Iran, and China, and has a diverse geography that includes mountains, plains, deserts, and a coastline along the Arabian Sea. Since its independence in 1947, Pakistan has experienced a complex political evolution involving cycles of democratic governance, military rule, and institutional instability. These dynamics have influenced its development trajectory, state capacity, and regional inequalities (Hippler et al., 2022; Ziring and Burki, 2025).

Demography

With a population exceeding 240 million, Pakistan is the world's fifth most populous country (Finance Division, 2025). The population is predominantly young—around 64 per cent is under the age of 30—offering a potential demographic dividend but also posing significant challenges in terms of job creation, education, and healthcare (Khan et al. 2016). Urbanization has accelerated in recent decades, with nearly 40 per cent of the population now residing in cities. This rapid shift has strained infrastructure and basic services, leading to the growth of informal settlements, air pollution, and inadequate waste management (Ahmed and Javed, 2022; Ziring and Burki, 2025).

Pakistan is ethnically and linguistically diverse, with major groups including Punjabis, Pashtuns, Sindhis, Baloch, and Muhajirs. Urdu is the national language, while English is used extensively in administration and education. The majority of the population practices Islam, with significant intra-faith diversity (Rahman, 2010; Ziring and Burki, 2025).

Economy

Pakistan's economy faces persistent structural challenges. Nearly 40 per cent of the population lives below the poverty line, with stark disparities between urban and rural areas in access to services such as education and healthcare (Finance Division, 2025). Agriculture remains a cornerstone of the economy, contributing about 23 per cent of GDP and employing over 37 per cent of the workforce. Key crops include wheat, cotton, and rice. However, the sector is highly vulnerable to climate shocks, water scarcity, and outdated infrastructure (Shahzad et al., 2021; Ahmed and Javed, 2022).

Industry, which accounts for 18 per cent of GDP, is largely driven by textiles and manufacturing. Although the energy sector is growing, it remains hampered by inefficiencies and supply

constraints. The services sector continues to expand, particularly in urban areas, but informality and underemployment remain widespread.

Rapid urbanization and demographic pressures have increased demand for jobs, housing, and social services. Economic reforms and international financial assistance—including from the IMF—have sought to stabilize macroeconomic conditions, but growth remains uneven and vulnerable to both internal and external shocks (Ahmed and Javed, 2022; Ziring and Burki, 2025).

Welfare

Pakistan's welfare system is centred around non-contributory social assistance programs, with the Benazir Income Support Program (BISP) as its flagship initiative, covering over 9 million households. According to the Pakistan Development Update (World Bank, 2025), recent reforms have aimed to improve targeting and efficiency through the National Socio-Economic Registry (NSER). However, the system faces persistent challenges related to fiscal constraints, limited coverage, and the adequacy of benefits. The government is transitioning from generalized subsidies to targeted cash transfers, but expanding and sustaining welfare provisions remains difficult amidst economic pressures (World Bank, 2025b).

Climate vulnerability

Pakistan is one of the most climate-vulnerable countries globally, ranked 8th on the Global Climate Risk Index. The country faces escalating environmental challenges, including rising temperatures, melting glaciers in the Himalayas, erratic monsoon patterns, and extreme weather events. The 2022 floods, which displaced over 33 million people and caused billions in damages, underscored the scale of Pakistan's exposure to climate risks.

Water security is under severe strain, compounded by inefficient water use, glacier retreat, and declining groundwater. Deforestation, desertification, air pollution, and biodiversity loss further exacerbate environmental degradation, particularly in rural and marginalized communities (Ministry of Climate Change, 2021; Government of Pakistan, 2025).

Climate policy and governance

Pakistan's climate strategy integrates both mitigation and adaptation, guided by principles of equity, resilience, and sustainable development. The National Climate Change Policy (Ministry of Climate Change, 2021) outlines targets for renewable energy development, climate-smart agriculture, and enhanced disaster preparedness. The Alternative and Renewable Energy Policy (Government of Pakistan, 2019) sets an ambitious goal of achieving 30 per cent renewable energy in the national mix by 2030.

Pakistan's updated Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) emphasize adaptation, which accounts for 70 per cent of their focus, prioritizing sectors such as water, agriculture, and urban resilience (Government of Pakistan, 2021; Government of Pakistan, 2025).

Major national initiatives include the Ten Billion Tree Tsunami Programme, which focuses on reforestation and ecosystem restoration, and the National Electric Vehicle Policy, aimed at reducing emissions in the transport sector.

Provincial governments have also taken steps toward localized climate action. For instance, Sindh and Punjab have promoted wind and solar energy projects. However, implementation remains inconsistent due to fiscal constraints, technical capacity gaps, and governance challenges.

Financing these commitments remains a significant hurdle, with heavy reliance on international climate funds and green bonds (Shamshad and Khawaha, 2025).

3.1.3. Sri Lanka

Sri Lanka is an island nation in the Indian Ocean, located just south of the Indian subcontinent, covering an area of approximately 65,000 square kilometres. The country is defined by a tropical climate and diverse ecological zones. Since gaining independence from British colonial rule in 1948, Sri Lanka has pursued a state-led development model with a strong emphasis on public services. This has resulted in relatively high human development indicators for a lower-middle-income country.

Governance has evolved through alternating periods of centralized authority, liberal reforms, and ethnic tensions. The country was embroiled in a protracted civil war from 1983 to 2009, largely rooted in ethnic conflict between the Sinhalese majority and Tamil minority. Despite post-war recovery and reconciliation efforts, underlying political divisions persist (Peiris and Arasaratnam, 2025).

Demography

Sri Lanka has a population of approximately 22 million. Life expectancy exceeds 75 years, and literacy is high among both men and women due to universal access to free primary, secondary and tertiary education. The population is ethnically and religiously diverse: the Sinhalese form the majority, while Tamils and Muslims constitute significant minorities. Sinhala and Tamil are both official languages, with English widely used for administrative and educational purposes (Peiris & Arasaratnam, 2025).

Economy

Sri Lanka's economy has undergone multiple transformations, especially since its liberalization in the 1970s. Services now account for nearly 50 per cent of employment, industry for 30 per cent, and agriculture for about 20 per cent. Remittances and tourism have emerged as leading foreign exchange earners. However, agriculture continues to support livelihoods in rural areas, even as its economic share has declined (Peiris & Arasaratnam, 2025).

Although poverty had declined to 4.1 per cent by 2016, recent shocks—including the COVID-19 pandemic and a 2022 debt crisis—reversed decades of progress. In 2022, Sri Lanka defaulted on its external debt, leading to hyperinflation, shortages of essential goods, and rising poverty. The IMF provided support, but recovery has been slow and painful (World Bank, 2023; Mudiyanse et al., 2024).

Inequality has widened over time, particularly since economic liberalization. Growth has not been pro-poor: consumption among the bottom 40 per cent has increased more slowly than among the top 20 per cent. Most of the poor live in rural areas, and a large portion of them work in agriculture. Educational disparities further reinforce inequality, with nearly 90 per cent of poor working-age adults having only primary education or less. Rural and estate sectors lag in access to quality education and health services. Vulnerable groups—including women, children, Malayaha Tamils, and the elderly—remain disproportionately affected by poverty and exclusion (Fernando, 2023; Mudiyanse et al., 2024; World Bank, 2023).

Welfare

Sri Lanka has a long-standing and broad welfare system dating back to the 1940s, characterized by extensive state involvement in education, healthcare, and subsidies for essential goods such as transport, fuel, and fertilizers. The system includes universal programs (e.g. free education and health care) and targeted schemes like Samurdhi, the main cash transfer program aimed at supporting poor households. Despite relatively high spending in South Asia (around 4.8 per cent of GDP in 2016), the system remains fragmented, lacks a unified strategy, and is vulnerable to political shifts and fiscal pressures. Challenges include inefficient targeting, inadequate benefit levels, and gaps in coverage, especially for vulnerable populations and poorer districts. Recent reforms stress the need for a cohesive, long-term social protection strategy that prioritizes equity, efficiency, and inclusion (Department of Census and Statistics, 2019; Fernando, 2023; Mudiyanse et al., 2024; World Bank, 2023; World Bank, 2025c).

Climate vulnerability

Sri Lanka is acutely vulnerable to climate change due to its island geography and dependence on climate-sensitive sectors. The country spans three main climatic zones: the Wet Zone (densely populated and industrialized southwest), the Dry Zone (agriculture-based north and east), and the Intermediate Zone bordering the central highlands. The country is already experiencing the effects of climate change: increased temperature, erratic rainfall, flash floods, landslides, droughts, sea-level rise, and extreme weather events. Projections indicate the Wet Zone will get wetter and the Dry Zone drier—intensifying both flood and drought risks. Agriculture, fisheries, and coastal communities are particularly exposed. At-risk groups include farmers, fisherfolk, the urban poor, women and children, elderly people, persons with disabilities, and Indigenous communities. Many of these groups rely on natural resources for their livelihoods and lack the adaptive capacity to respond to environmental change (Climate Change Secretariat, 2016).

Climate policy and governance

Sri Lanka ratified the Paris Agreement in 2016 and submitted updated Nationally Determined Contributions in 2021 (Ministry of Environment, 2021). These are supported by the National Adaptation Plan (NAP) 2016–2025 (Climate Change Secretariat, 2016), which focuses on enhancing the resilience of individuals, communities, and ecosystems across key sectors such as agriculture, water, health, and coastal systems.

Adaptation is a key policy focus, given the country's low share of global emissions—just 0.08 per cent, or 1.02 tonnes per capita. Despite this, Sri Lanka has pledged a 14.5 per cent emissions reduction by 2030. Key mitigation strategies include expanding renewable energy, promoting sustainable agriculture, and improving disaster preparedness. Institutionally, Sri Lanka has developed a national climate strategy, supported by dedicated agencies and policies on climate finance and resilience. Key initiatives include renewable energy expansion, climate-smart agriculture, early warning systems, and efforts toward long-term carbon neutrality (Climate Change Secretariat, 2023; Ministry of Environment, 2023).

3.2. European country profiles

3.2.1. Hungary

Hungary is a landlocked Central European country situated in the Carpathian Basin, bordered by seven countries. It has a 1000-year history of statehood, initially marked by relative independence, and later shaped by periods of Ottoman, Habsburg, and Soviet influence, before transitioning to democracy after 1989. Since joining the European Union in 2004, Hungary has undergone extensive legal, economic, and institutional transformation, though democratic backsliding and centralized governance under the Orbán administration have drawn international scrutiny since ca. 2010 (Berend and Vardy, 2025).

Demography

Hungary faces significant demographic challenges. The population is projected to fall below 9.6 million in 2025 due to persistently low fertility rates (1.5 in 2023), population ageing (old age dependency ratio of 32 per cent in 2024), and net emigration. Emigration, particularly among skilled youth, continues to drain sectors such as healthcare, IT, and innovation. Temporary immigration of third-country nationals into low-skilled jobs in construction, manufacturing-industry and services such as couriers, elderly care and hospitality does little to offset the brain drain.

While the national employment rate reached 74.1 per cent in 2024, regional disparities persist. Rural areas in northeastern and southwestern Hungary face low employment and high inactivity, especially among women and low-skilled workers. In contrast, Budapest and its metropolitan area and industrial zones in western Hungary report stronger labour market participation (Tóth, 2023).

Economy

Hungary is one of the most manufacturing-intensive economies in the EU, with automotive, electronics, and battery production anchoring its export profile. This structure attracts foreign investment but creates vulnerability to external shocks, as evident during the 2022–2024 period of energy disruptions, inflation, and declining consumer demand. By 2024, real GDP growth had slowed to 0.6 per cent, and industrial output fell 5.5 per cent year-on-year, with further contraction reported in 2025 (KSH, 2024a, 2024b).

Moreover, A significant share of public funds and a broad array of economic sectors (from energy and agriculture to tourism and media) have been directed toward businesses closely linked to the national political elite, influencing Hungary's economic efficiency, growth and competitiveness (Zeisler, 2023; OECD, 2025).

The Hungarian government has actively supported the development of the e-mobility and battery sectors through targeted industrial policies and investment incentives (NFFT, 2023). However, the OECD (2025) notes that regulatory oversight remains limited, environmental assessments need strengthening, and mechanisms for community consultation are weak – raising concerns about the long-term environmental and social sustainability of this industrial strategy.

Welfare

Hungary's welfare system combines universal and means-tested benefits but faces persistent challenges related to fiscal constraints, underinvestment, and social inequality. According to the

OECD (2025), social spending remains below the EU average, with limited coverage and adequacy for low-income groups. Reforms have prioritized family-related tax benefits that tend to favor higher-income households, while employment-related and minimum income supports are weak by OECD standards.

Climate vulnerability

Hungary is increasingly affected by climate-related risks. Drought frequency has risen, particularly in the Southern Great Plain, leading to reduced agricultural yields and water insecurity. Flood risks along the Danube and Tisza rivers are rising due to changing precipitation and snowmelt patterns. Urban areas, including Budapest, experience intensifying heat island effects that disproportionately impact vulnerable populations such as the elderly (NFFT, 2023; OECD, 2023).

Climate impacts are unevenly distributed across regions and social groups. Agriculture-dependent rural communities face compounded risks from poverty, ageing populations, and inadequate infrastructure, limiting their adaptive capacity.

Climate policy and governance

Hungary adopted the National Framework Strategy on Sustainable Development (NFSSD) in 2013, emphasizing intergenerational equity and prudent management of natural, social, and human capital. The National Council for Sustainable Development (NFFT) monitors implementation, issuing biennial reviews. The latest 2023 report identified improvements in material efficiency but declines in institutional trust, education, and life satisfaction (NFFT, 2023).

Climate governance has expanded since 2008, with a series of national strategies including the National Climate Change Strategies (NCCS I and II), the Climate Protection Action Plans, and Hungary's Long-Term Climate Strategy to 2050 (Government of Hungary, 2020). These documents outline mitigation and adaptation goals, such as climate neutrality by 2050, expansion of renewables, and resilience building (European Commission, 2025; Green Policy Centre, 2025).

However, institutional weaknesses persist. Hungary has lacked a dedicated Ministry for the Environment since 2010. Responsibilities are dispersed across ministries and local offices, weakening enforcement and coordination. A landmark 2025 Constitutional Court ruling declared the 2020 Climate Act unconstitutional due to vague targets and lack of enforceability, urging stronger legal foundations (Alkotmánybíróság, 2025).

Despite these challenges, Hungary has achieved notable progress. Greenhouse gas emissions fell by 33 per cent from 1990 to 2021, and solar energy now supplies 24 per cent of national electricity. Still, wind energy is stalled due to restrictive permitting laws, and transport emissions are rising, especially from road freight (Green Policy Centre, 2025; NEKT, 2024).

Key policy recommendations from the NFFT and Constitutional Court include strengthening climate legislation, balancing investment across capital types, enabling wind power, tailoring adaptation in lagging regions, improving institutional coordination, and mainstreaming climate into all policy domains (NFFT, 2023; Alkotmánybíróság, 2025).

3.2.2. Italy

Italy is a Southern European country occupying a long peninsula and surrounding islands, including Sicily and Sardinia, bordered by the Mediterranean Sea. Its diverse geography includes Alpine mountains in the north, rolling plains in the Po Valley, and a long coastline susceptible to erosion and sea-level rise. Italy has a rich cultural and political history dating back to ancient Rome, transitioning into a unified modern state in 1861. Since World War II, it has operated as a parliamentary republic with a high level of decentralization, granting significant autonomy to regions (Larner and Powell, 2025).

Demography and economy

Italy has a population of approximately 59 million and has one of the oldest populations in Europe (old age dependency ratio of 39 per cent in 2024). Low fertility rates and increasing life expectancy pose challenges for workforce sustainability and the welfare system. Youth unemployment remains high, and labour market participation among women is below the EU average (Larner & Powell, 2025). The country has seen persistent regional inequalities, with the southern regions experiencing lower employment, higher poverty, and weaker infrastructure.

Economically, Italy is among the world's largest economies, with strengths in manufacturing, design, and tourism. However, sluggish growth, high public debt, and structural inefficiencies have constrained development. Informal work and tax evasion further undermine fiscal capacity. Despite these challenges, Italy remains a key member of the EU and the Eurozone, with strong export sectors and growing investment in green innovation (OECD, 2024a).

Welfare

Italy's welfare system provides a broad mix of social protections—including pensions, healthcare, and family support—but faces significant challenges with fragmentation, inefficiencies, and unequal coverage. According to the OECD Economic Survey: Italy 2023, public social spending is high, particularly on pensions, but benefits for working-age individuals and families are relatively limited, and poverty risks remain high, especially among young people and children (OECD, 2024a).

Climate vulnerability

Italy is one of Europe's climate "hotspots," warming at twice the global average. Climate change is already impacting agriculture, water resources, public health, and biodiversity. Between 2016 and 2020, 41.6 per cent of Italy's land experienced drought conditions, with 2022 causing an estimated €6 billion in agricultural losses. Northern Italy, heavily reliant on river-fed irrigation, has been particularly affected by reduced snowpack and water shortages. Urban areas face worsening air quality and heatwaves—over 18,000 heat-related deaths were recorded in 2022 alone (AsviS, 2024).

Rising sea levels threaten low-lying coastal zones and infrastructure, with estimated damages ranging from €50 to €81 billion by 2050. Poor and marginalised communities, especially in southern regions and urban peripheries, are disproportionately affected by heat, food insecurity, and limited adaptive capacity, reinforcing social and spatial inequalities (AsviS, 2024).

Climate policy and governance

Italy's climate strategy operates within the broader European Green Deal framework, supported by mechanisms such as the EU Just Transition Mechanism and the Recovery and Resilience Facility. At the national level, several policy instruments guide climate and energy planning. The National Strategy for Sustainable Development, revised in 2023, provides Italy's overarching framework for implementing the 2030 Agenda. It emphasizes multilevel governance, regional action plans, and broad public participation. However, despite being formally approved by the State-Regions Conference, its implementation has stalled (AsviS, 2024).

The National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan (NECP), outlines decarbonization targets but has been criticized by civil society organizations and energy experts for prolonging reliance on fossil fuels, particularly through support for carbon capture and storage (CCS). The plan also promotes nuclear energy, which some view as a costly distraction from investment in renewable energy. Critics argue that the NECP underestimates the country's renewable energy potential, lacks robust governance mechanisms, and was developed with limited public consultation and transparency (ECCO, 2024; Lisi and Fantozzi, 2024).

In parallel, the 2022 Constitutional Amendment marked a significant legal development by elevating environmental protection and intergenerational justice to constitutional principles (Gazzetta Ufficiale della Repubblica Italiana, 2022). It established environmental protection as an "absolute value" and requires all new legislation to undergo generational impact assessments, ensuring that the interests of future generations are considered in policymaking (Pollera, 2022).

Despite these legislative advances, Italy remains off track to meet its EU climate targets for 2030 and 2050. Greenhouse gas emissions have declined only modestly between 2010 and 2022, and recent rebounds following the COVID-19 pandemic have stalled progress. In 2022, renewable energy accounted for just 19.1 per cent of final energy consumption—far below the 42.5 per cent target for 2030 (AsviS, 2024).

3.2.3. Netherlands

The Netherlands is a low-lying, densely populated country located in Northwestern Europe, situated along the North Sea coast. With a population of around 18 million in 2025, it is one of the most densely populated countries in Europe. Politically, the Netherlands is a constitutional monarchy with a long-standing parliamentary democracy. It is a founding member of the European Union and plays an active role in EU policymaking, particularly in areas related to trade, climate policy, and digital governance.

The country has a long tradition of social democracy, consensus-based governance, and environmental management. Its political landscape has long been shaped by the "polder model", a cross-party and multi-stakeholder approach to negotiation and compromise on social, economic, and environmental issues (Schreuder, 2001).

The first National Environmental Policy Plan introduced in 1989 was based on this corporatist approach rooted on cooperation, consensus building, and democratic self-rule.

Four ministries (Climate Policy and Green Growth; Infrastructure and Water Management; Agriculture, Fisheries, Food Security and Nature; Housing and Spatial Planning) reflect decades of policy attention to land use, water management, and environmental protection, building on an

institutional legacy shaped by flood risk management, intensive agriculture, and dense urban development. This institutional density positions the Netherlands as an international reference point for climate adaptation and integrated environmental planning.

The Netherlands has also played a prominent role in global sustainability debates, including as a key actor in international water governance and climate adaptation, drawing on its extensive experience with flood control and integrated spatial planning. For example, the Dutch Delta Programme and Delta Works (<https://english.deltaprogramma.nl>), a system of dams and storm surge barriers constructed in the 1950s-1990s to protect the southwest of the country from the sea, have become international benchmarks for large-scale climate adaptation and coastal resilience planning. More recently, the Netherlands co-founded the Global Commission on Adaptation (<https://gca.org>, 2018) and continues to lead initiatives on climate-resilient water management within the UN and multilateral development banks.

Demography and economy

The Netherlands faces its own demographic challenges, shaped by population ageing and persistent regional disparities. The old-age dependency ratio continues to rise (projected at around 40 per cent in 2030, Economic Policy Committee - Ageing Working Group, 2023), also on account of a fertility rate declining over time, although with some positive fluctuations in recent years (approximately 1.69 children per woman in 2025). Population growth is driven mainly by immigration, particularly in major urban areas such as Amsterdam, Rotterdam, The Hague, and Utrecht. These cities have become highly multicultural, with more than half of residents under 35 having a migrant background. At the same time, peripheral, rural regions face population stagnation or decline.

The Netherlands has one of Europe's most open and globally integrated economies, characterized by high levels of trade, foreign investment, and advanced logistics. It combines a competitive private sector with strong social partnership traditions and an active welfare state. The Dutch economy is diversified across agriculture and food processing, high-tech manufacturing, chemicals, logistics, and business services. The Port of Rotterdam is Europe's largest; together with Amsterdam's Schiphol Airport, they form critical nodes in global supply chains. Agriculture plays an outsized role despite the Netherlands' small size: it is one of the world's top agricultural exporters, supported by intensive production systems and advanced agri-tech.

Welfare

The Netherlands combines high levels of economic development, digitalization, and global trade integration with strong social welfare traditions. Despite high levels of education and digital literacy, social inequalities persist between urban and rural regions, and between homeowners and tenants in the energy transition. In 2022, the Netherlands had an income Gini coefficient of 0.285, indicating relatively low-income inequality by international standards. Wealth inequality, however, was considerably higher at 0.711. Notably, wealth inequality declined sharply between 2015 and 2022, largely due to rising house prices that increased the net wealth of a broader share of households (CBS Statistics Netherlands, 2024).

Energy system and climate vulnerability

The Netherlands' energy system is in the midst of a complex transition away from its historic dependence on natural gas. For decades, large onshore reserves—especially the Groningen gas field—underpinned domestic heating, electricity generation, and exports, but induced earthquakes and climate commitments have accelerated the phase-out of gas extraction (Bakema et al., 2018). Today, the energy mix still relies significantly on fossil fuels, yet renewables—particularly offshore wind in the North Sea, onshore wind, and solar—are expanding rapidly. In 2024, renewable sources

accounted only for 19.8 per cent of gross national energy consumption CBS (CBS Statistics Netherlands, 2025). The country also functions as an important energy hub for Northwest Europe, with major import, storage, and transit infrastructure for gas, oil products, and electricity. This hub role, combined with high per-capita energy use and dense urban–industrial clusters, makes the Dutch energy transition both particularly challenging and strategically significant for the wider region.

The Netherlands is highly vulnerable to climate change due to its low-lying geography (approximately one-third of its territory lies below sea level). Rising sea levels, increased precipitation, and river flooding threaten both infrastructure and livelihoods. Climate adaptation is therefore not only an environmental necessity but a core element of national security and spatial planning. Decades of expertise in water management underpin the country’s resilience strategies, which integrates flood protection, freshwater supply, and spatial adaptation, including land reclamation from the sea. While the country ranks among the world’s top food exporters, its livestock-intensive farming system and heavy reliance on fossil fuels in transport and industry create significant environmental pressures.

Climate policy and governance

The country’s long-standing expertise in water management, spatial planning, and climate adaptation also shapes economic priorities, especially as sea-level rise and extreme weather create new pressures. The main principles guiding Dutch climate mitigation and adaptation rest on legal commitments to have an energy system by 2050 with greenhouse gas emissions that are 95 per cent lower than in 1990. The country has also committed to achieve climate neutrality by 2050, as set out in the Dutch Climate Law (Klimaatwet, 2019, updated in 2023). These targets are operationalized through the Climate Agreement (Government of the Netherlands, 2019), which defines transition pathways across five sectors: electricity, built environment, industry, mobility, and agriculture (Erbach, 2024). The National Climate and Energy Plan (2020–2030) and the Dutch Fund for Climate and Development (established in 2020) further support investments in renewable energy, green hydrogen, and sustainable mobility. The Netherlands is also a key contributor to the EU Green Deal and Fit for 55 package.

However, implementation of sustainability policies and measures has exposed deep social and economic tensions, particularly in the agricultural sector over nitrogen emissions, biodiversity loss, and land-use conflicts (see, e.g., Ryan and Hoes, 2025). The landmark Greenpeace Nederland vs the Dutch State ruling in 2025, requiring compliance with nitrogen reduction targets, exemplifies the mounting legal and political pressure (Polderman, 2025). More broadly, the energy and agricultural transitions have spurred debates over fairness, participation, and regional equity.

Furthermore, in recent years there has been steady opposition to the construction of energy- and water-hungry data centres. Communities have protested the expansion of hyperscale data centres, particularly in regions like the Wieringermeer and Zeewolde (e.g., Meaker, 2022). Residents and activists argued that these facilities consume disproportionate amounts of energy and water, strain local infrastructure, and offer limited economic benefits. As a result, the city of Amsterdam has imposed a moratorium on data centre expansion (Gooding, 2024; *NL Times*, 2025). The protests highlighted growing public concern about how large tech infrastructures shape land use, sustainability goals, and democratic oversight, and resulted in the country being perceived as “hostile” towards the tech industry.

3.2.4. Norway

Norway is a mountainous and fjord-rich country located in Northern Europe, occupying the western portion of the Scandinavian Peninsula. With a population of around 5.6 million in 2025, it is one of the most sparsely populated countries in Europe. Politically, Norway is a constitutional monarchy with a strong parliamentary democracy. It is not a member of the European Union but participates in the European Economic Area, granting it access to the EU single market (Sandvik and Joys, 2025).

The country has a long tradition of social democracy and environmentalism. Norway established one of the world's first Ministries of Environment in 1972, and its political landscape has long been shaped by cross-party consensus on climate and welfare policies. Norway's contributions to global environmental leadership includes the Brundtland Commission in the 1980s, which introduced the concept of sustainable development to the global agenda (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987; Schoyen and Takle, 2022).

Demography

Even if population ageing is less advanced in Norway than in most other European countries (old age dependency ratio of 29 per cent in 2024) also Norway faces demographic challenges due to a declining birth rate (1.4 children per woman in 2024 compared with 1.9 in 1990) and an ageing population. Immigration remains a key driver of population growth, especially in urban areas. Indigenous Sámi communities face particular pressures from climate change and land-use conflicts tied to energy and resource development (Sandvik and Joys, 2025).

Economy

Norway has one of the world's wealthiest and most stable economies, supported by a combination of natural resource wealth—particularly petroleum—and a highly developed welfare state (Andersen et al., 2017; Schoyen et al., 2022). The country belongs to a Nordic version of 'coordinated market economies', combining a dynamic but regulated private sector with significant state ownership in strategic sectors such as energy, transport, and finance (Hall and Soskice, 2001; Mjøset and Cappelen, 2011). The state retains significant ownership in key sectors such as energy and finance, operating within what Hall and Soskice (2001) describe as a "coordinated market economy". The Government Pension Fund Global, funded by oil revenues, is the world's largest sovereign wealth fund and underpins Norway's long-term fiscal and intergenerational equity (OECD, 2024b).

The petroleum sector remains vital, accounting for about 20 per cent of GDP and 40 per cent of exports. However, it also contributes nearly half of Norway's domestic greenhouse gas emissions, presenting policy tensions between economic growth and climate commitments. The rest of the economy is diversified across maritime shipping, aquaculture, hydropower, and technology services (OECD, 2022, 2024b). Norway maintains high levels of productivity and one of the lowest inequality rates globally, which is reflected in the IHDI.

Energy system and climate vulnerability

Norway's electricity system is nearly 100 per cent renewable, dominated by large-scale hydropower and increasingly supplemented by wind energy. Electrification of transport and industry has progressed rapidly, with electric vehicles (EVs) making up the majority of new car sales, supported by tax exemptions and toll waivers. Nevertheless, fossil fuels still dominate energy use in sectors such as offshore oil operations and some industrial processes (OECD, 2022)

Norway is exposed to both physical and transition risks from climate change. Physical risks include more intense rainfall, landslides, coastal erosion, and rising temperatures that threaten biodiversity, infrastructure, and agricultural systems. Transition risks involve the declining value of petroleum assets and pressures to decarbonize heavy industries. Climate vulnerabilities are unevenly distributed, with Northern Norway and remote communities facing higher exposure to energy insecurity and poor infrastructure (Det Kongelige Klima- Og Miljødepartement, 2023).

Climate policy and governance

Norwegian climate policy operates within the framework of the UNFCCC, the Kyoto Protocol, and the Paris Agreement. Norway committed to reducing emissions by 70 per cent from 1990 levels by 2030. This target is legally embedded in the Climate Act (2017) (Klima- og miljødepartementet, 2017), which mandates updated emissions goals every five years and integrates climate accounting into national budget processes.

Norway collaborates closely with the EU through the Emissions Trading System (ETS) and the Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR), covering industrial, energy, transport, and agricultural emissions. A notable feature of Norwegian climate politics is the cross-party climate compromise, which has provided long-term policy stability and supported a broad consensus on reducing emissions and transitioning to a low-carbon economy (OECD, 2022).

National policies include a longstanding CO₂ tax (established in 1991), large-scale support for carbon capture and storage (CCS), and renewable energy incentives. Projects like Longship and Northern Lights aim to commercialize offshore CO₂ storage, leveraging Norway's offshore expertise. Local governments play a crucial role in implementing climate strategies, managing spatial planning, local transport, and recycling, guided by state frameworks that promote climate-resilient land use (OECD, 2022).

Environmental rights are also constitutionally protected. Article §112 of the Norwegian Constitution guarantees citizens the right to a healthy environment, requiring public authorities to ensure sustainable natural resource use and provide environmental information (The Norwegian Parliament, 1814; Takle, 2025).

4. Research design and method

Research teams in the seven selected countries organised workshops where the participants were invited to play the SPES version of *Le Grand Jeu (LGJ)*, followed by a structured group discussion. The workshops functioned as a variation of the focus group method—whose value lies in allowing researchers to observe meaning-making and conflict as they emerge through interaction—except that here the discussion was triggered by engagement in play (Acocella and Cataldi, 2021; Malpass et al., 2023; Wibeck and Neset, 2020). Gameplay served, above all, as a prompt and conversation starter but in some instances also as a device to break hierarchies, enabling laypersons to participate more confidently through fiction, role-taking, and the subversion of everyday social positions. After the workshops, participants were invited to share their reflections on the themes explored as well as the workshop dynamics in short individual follow-up semi-structured interviews.

LGJ proved to be an effective and efficient method to involve non-experts in complex policy discussions, while leaving room for creativity and individual and collective exploration. In our view, the approach has three unique features:

- It makes room for creativity to emerge in a relatively (un)structured setting that triggers the generation of unusual, bold ideas that are, however, grounded in lived realities and people's perceptions. This is why LGJ elicits a perspective on people's opinions that are usually not captured by surveys or other quantitative instruments.
- It encourages people, including non-experts that often feel disempowered and not invited to the policy debate, to speak up their mind and be seen. In this sense, it fosters people's empowerment, especially among vulnerable groups (e.g., migrants and the elderly who participated in the Dutch workshops).
- The collective dimension of ideas exchange contributes to awareness-raising and allows for empathy between distinct people with diverse views to emerge. In this respect, LGJ contributes to raising people's alertness about the sustainability transition and improving their understanding of the associated trade-offs.

A further description and discussion of the method will be provided in a forthcoming, updated version of the game manual designed for the SPES version of the *Le Grand Jeu (LGJ)*. The manual will be made available on the SPES project website.

4.1. The overall frame of the workshops

The workshops were generally facilitated by at least two *researchers*. In the game section of the workshop, one researcher acted as *Game Master (GM)* – leading the game process, guiding the narrative, and modelling the consequences of players' actions – while the other acted as the *Observer*, who supported the Game Master and took field notes, documenting the players' actions, narratives, decisions and as well as the themes that emerged in the game. In the post-game discussions, the two researchers jointly facilitated a semi-structured group conversation using a discussion guide (see Appendix), prompting reflections on the game experience and eliciting participants' perspectives on aspirations, challenges, and policy solutions related to sustainable human development.

Le Grand Jeu (LGJ) was adapted and redesigned to the purposes of SPES through an inclusive process, which was supported and facilitated by Federico Bonneli, one of the creators of the game. The constructed SPES scenario of *Le Grand Jeu (LGJ)* depicted a fictional society consisting of

interconnected urban and rural areas, typically divided by a body of water—such as a river or sea — as well as a wilderness area. This game scenario immerses players in the roles of residents making life and livelihood decisions while navigating the tensions between economic productivity, social equity, and environmental sustainability. Whether this setting was interpreted as representing a local community or a broader national context varied across the national workshops.

Image 2: *Adaption of LGJ to SPES*

Gameplay unfolded on two modular boards composed of grid-based tiles. These tiles represented areas connected to societal infrastructure, where players would establish the private and economic activities associated with their roles. Alternatively, they could choose to set up their lives outside the grid, in areas lacking such infrastructure. The game is turn-based. In the initial round, participants created their roles and placed their homes and economic activities on the board, marked with their respective colour of playdough. Players could decide to set up a farm or a factory, work with technology and innovation, and so forth. In subsequent rounds, players could take actions to develop and adapt their lives in the simulated society—for example, by making investments, inventing new technologies, or proposing public policies. The economic, social and environmental consequences of their actions were simulated through discussions with the game master and the rolling of dice. Through the activities, players could acquire resources that they could invest, but also externalities that affected their common natural environment. Furthermore, the GM could use event cards and a randomized wheel of fortune to introduce uncertainty and simulate socio-environmental shocks and policy shifts.

Image 3 *Examples of game setup in Italy and Hungary*

As the consequences of individual actions and event cards unfolded, players faced collective action dilemmas—such as managing shared resources and deciding whether to invest in collective infrastructure—while negotiating trade-offs between personal gain and broader societal impacts. Player interaction, both direct and indirect, became central: they could negotiate, cooperate, or compete, and the effects of one player’s choices (such as pollution, innovation, or policy) often rippled across the board, influencing others. This interplay fostered a dynamic and evolving environment in which cooperation, conflict, and institutional responses were key to navigating the game’s challenges. The open-ended structure, narrative facilitation, and evolving resource economy were deliberately configured to surface real-world analogues to sustainability dilemmas, including social stratification, ecological limits, and institutional trust. While the resources represented the economic dimension and the externalities represented the environmental dimension, the social dimension was captured through discussions among players, particularly as they evaluated the social atmosphere of their simulated society.

While the workshops were guided by a shared methodological framework, the co-created implementation manual explicitly endorsed contextual adaptation. National research teams were granted flexibility to adjust the SPES scenario – such as the exact framing of the narrative or role assignments – and to calibrate specific game mechanics to reflect local priorities and conditions. GMs tailored collective and individual event cards to local contexts and had discretion to adjust gameplay, provided the core aim of stimulating meaningful discussion on sustainability transitions was maintained. Country specific adaptations ranged from the removal of the wheel (Norway) to customized scoring systems (Norway, Sri Lanka) and context-specific event cards (Netherlands).

This flexibility enabled both contextual relevance and methodological experimentation, allowing the game to be explored not only as a structured research tool but also as a space for participatory engagement and learning. While the overarching structure ensured a degree of comparability across countries, local adaptations introduced productive variation. The balance between local responsiveness and adherence to shared research goals helped preserve the analytical coherence of the project while allowing insights to emerge that were deeply grounded in diverse national settings. These variations are not comprehensively examined in this report, which focuses on the thematic substance and reflections that emerged in the workshops. The methodological aspects and technical choices related to the games themselves are instead addressed in the forthcoming game manual and playbook.

4.2. The workshops across the seven countries

The SPES workshops were implemented in seven countries—Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Kenya, Sri Lanka, and Pakistan. While the original proposal envisioned recruiting participants who were particularly vulnerable to the negative impacts of climate change and climate policies—both as individual citizens and as representatives of civil society organizations—the recruitment strategy evolved over the course of the project. Recognizing the political, social, and institutional diversity across the participating countries, the project adopted a pragmatic and context-sensitive approach to recruitment. Each country team developed its own criteria and strategy for participant selection and recruitment, ensuring the workshops were both locally relevant and inclusive of diverse perspectives. A qualitative approach like this will not achieve statistical representativeness. Instead, the point was to include a diversity of voices. The implementation manual recommended 4–6 participants per session, with attention to socio-economic, occupational, and cultural diversity, and an overarching aim to reflect different interests and vulnerabilities in relation to climate transition policies.

Table 1 below summarizes the configuration of the workshops in each country, including the number of sessions conducted, participant characteristics, and the extent of individual follow-up interviews, documentation and recruitments strategy.

Table 1: Workshop composition

COUNTRY	NO. OF WORKSHOPS & PARTICIPANTS (IN TOTAL)	PARTICIPANT PROFILES	INTERVIEWS	DOCUMENTATION	RECRUITMENT STRATEGY
Hungary	3 workshops 16 participants Gender: 7F/9M Age: 18-57	All workshops in the Capital Budapest. Sessions 1 and 2: mostly tertiary educated. Session 3: group of 18-year-old secondary students	14	Audio, video, field notes, photos	Snowballing from network of researchers, and purposive sampling through Facebook post
Italy	3 workshops 15 participants Gender: 11F/4M	Two workshops in the City of Florence, one in the small town of Lucca. Session 1: university students; Session 2: health/social operators; Session 3: social cooperative staff	9	Audio, field notes, photos	Invitation in an online group chat at university and in professional communities
Netherlands	4 workshops 23 participants Gender: 12F/11M Age: 14-60s	All workshops in the Capital, Amsterdam. Session 1: students and researchers; Session 2 & Session 3: artists, academics, health professionals, media professional, housewives; Session 4: senior citizens, migrants	4	Audio, photos, field notes	Internet forums, library flyers, word of mouth, via community centre
Norway	3 workshops 11 participants Gender: 6F/5M Age: 24-65	All workshops in the Capital Oslo. Recruited from diverse civil society organizations across sectors	6	Audio, video, field notes, photos	Direct email contact with national civil society organizations

Kenya	2 workshops 10 participants Gender: 4F/6M Age: 20-60	Both workshops in the Capital of Nairobi Community members, public institution professionals, civil society leaders	2	Audio, video, field notes, photos	Network and snowball, and purposive sampling
Pakistan	2 workshops 20 participants Gender: 9F/11M Age: 25-70	Workshops were held in the cities of Islamabad and Rawalpindi Multisectoral professional backgrounds from public-, private- and civil society sector	7	Field notes	Purposive sampling based on expertise and thematic relevance
Sri Lanka	3 workshops 13 participants Gender: 9F/4M Age: 34-70	2 Workshops in the capital Colombo, 1 workshop in a rural area. 1 session with professional. 1 session with civil society representatives working with vulnerable groups. 1 session with vulnerable citizens (e.g. farmers)	11	Audio, sporadic video, field notes, photos	Network and snowball

Across the seven countries, workshops followed the shared structure of gameplay, group discussion, and (whenever possible) individual interviews. Participant profiles varied in line with the national approaches to the workshops –some teams prioritized professional or civil society actors, while others engaged youth, senior citizens, or vulnerable groups, including migrants. The comprehensiveness and number of post-game interviews differed, with Hungary and Italy conducting the most, while Kenya, Netherlands, and Sri Lanka reported limited on-record follow-up conversations.

4.3. Analytical Framework: Aspirations, Problems and Solutions and thematic analysis

The analyses of workshop findings were done by the local research teams in the seven countries and were guided by a shared conceptual framework centred on three interrelated dimensions: *aspirations*, *problems*, and *policy solutions*. This triad structured both the facilitation of post-game discussions and the subsequent interpretation of data. Participants were invited to reflect on the kinds of societies they wished to live in (aspirations), the obstacles that stand in the way of achieving them (problems or challenges), and the measures that could enable progress (policy solutions). Framing discussions in this way allowed for a consistent yet flexible structure to capture diverse views on ecological sustainability and human development, while ensuring alignment with the overarching goals of the SPES project—namely, reconciling efforts to promote productivity, equity, ecological sustainability and participation.

Within this common framework, each country team conducted a bottom-up thematic analysis of their workshop materials—including transcripts, field notes, and observation reports. Rather than applying a fixed coding scheme, themes were inductively derived from participants' own language and concerns, allowing country teams to surface context-specific insights while preserving the richness of locally grounded narratives. These themes were then organized under the overarching categories of aspirations, problems, and policy solutions, enabling structured comparison across sites without flattening national particularities. This approach ensured that the analysis remained responsive to the specificities of the country contexts and participants' lived experiences while contributing to a coherent cross-country synthesis.

Next, in Section 5 we present the empirical findings from the workshops. More specifically, we detail the themes that emerged from the game events and related discussions in each of the country cases. It should be noted that the separation into distinct themes is an analytical construct resulting from the researchers' choices based on their interpretations of the data. In practice, several of the highlighted themes are entangled and often highly interconnected.

5. Findings

5.1. Global South

5.1.1. Kenya

The LGJ workshops and group discussions in Kenya were designed to understand the drivers of public support for and opposition against transiting trajectories towards more socially and environmentally sustainable societies. Table 2 summarises the key themes in terms of aspirations, key transition challenges policy ideas and priorities, while the subsequent sub-sections below elaborate further on the topics discussed in Kenya.

Table 2: Summary of findings in Kenya

THEME	ASPIRATIONS	KEY CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS	POLICY PRIORITIES AND IDEAS	ACTORS (PERCEIVED RELEVANT ACTORS AND THEIR ROLES)
Incentives	Increased uptake of environmentally sustainable measures	High taxation by the government and a lack of incentives to adopt sustainable practices	Lower taxes rates Incentives like tax rebates on businesses that adopt environmentally sustainable practices	Government - to change tax laws Provision of rebates and incentives for sustainable practices
Collective action and inclusion	Inclusive society Joint ownership of resources Collective responsibility Equity	Economic precarity forces citizens to prioritize short-term livelihood needs.	Better social safety nets and accessible social services	Government and community leaders – pursue inclusion
Equity and responsibility	Collective ownership of benefits of growth	Political and economic elite bypassing laws without action from government	Enforcement of laws and regulations	Government and local administration

Tensions between individual needs and collective interests

Collective action is important in ensuring environmental sustainability. From the workshop and the individual interviews, it emerged that these are difficult aspects to balance. While sustainability is desirable and an aspiration that any society embodies, it may be a difficult balance to achieve. In Kenya for instance, people with business interests rarely consider the effect of their investment on the environment and the extent to which the investment may affect sustainability. Little consideration is paid on the repercussions of actions like investments especially that which is industrial in nature. Government enforcement on environmental degradation or on matters sustainability is weak.

More specifically, tensions exist between individual needs and collective interests as individuals feel a need for “progress” or “personal development”. These steps taken by citizens include setting up business or engaging in a “hustle” that brings in money. A large part of this aspect is driven by a minimal state which offers limited public and social services. In a context where government’s investment in social services is limited, citizens are forced to access these services through markets. Citizens are therefore expected to pay for services like education and health with the responsibility and the high cost and of access falling on households. The commodification of public and social services, a situation where markets become the dominant mode of access, hurts the poor more exposing them to shocks. With the commodification of social services people have to supplement their income through other means to make ends meet for them and their households. Coupled with informality in labour, many Kenyans feel they need to secure their livelihoods through their own means against shocks and risks. As is typical of low-income countries, there is a large informal economy with precarious jobs and livelihoods. As a result, many Kenyans feel the need to find protection as the jobs they hold are insufficient at meeting their needs. With little government provision of social protection, safety nets lack for many.

These aspects were evidenced during the game, *Le Grand Jeu (LGJ)*, as most participants sought to establish businesses and other income-generating activities. Players felt the need to create wealth through individual means to cushion themselves from risks. Instead of collective action, participants sought individual means of protection in the absence of state provision. In seeking individual interest, little attention is paid to environmental sustainability and equity and at times individual interests are inimical to collective interests. A lack of government guarantee on social protection like old age pensions and other old age guarantees forces individuals to address their social and economic security through accumulation. Both covariate and idiosyncratic shocks pose a risk to society, but this can be smoothed through government support. Unexpected illnesses of a family member for instance may require that households have to pay for medical services themselves constraining and leading many to debt.

Political interests and the political class also fuel environmental degradation with politicians easily get away without penalties. A case mentioned for instance is where the rich and political elite are setting up private resorts for tourism in forested areas like Karura Forest and Ngong Forests at the expense of communities with no repercussions. The political elite get away with environmental degradation while making fortunes of money from their ventures.

Intergenerational equity

Younger and more educated people are keen on incorporating environmental sustainability than older less educated individuals. In both games, older individuals were keen at pursuing individual enterprises and other money-making ventures unlike the younger ones who set up environmentally sustainable ventures. Whereas the effects of climate change are visible and affect all people (though not proportionately), older individuals were less attentive to matters related to

sustainability. For older individuals there was little sense of intergenerational equity, while the younger players through their choices sought to create sustainable futures for themselves and for others. Pursuits of accumulation easily clouded consideration for future generations. Younger people on the other hand may be more aware of environmental sustainability as they could be more exposed through education and other content to global discussions on the matter. They had much more awareness and sense of equity and justice questioning others investment decisions. Increased debate on social media and other online content makes younger people more involved in debates of climate change, equity and environmental sustainability hence influenced their choices, and discussions during the game.

Taxation and incentives

Government incentives towards climate change are low making it difficult for those who wish to invest in efforts that would encourage sustainability. Participants in the study lamented that the government of Kenya does not provides sufficient incentives for people who want to put up investments that are climate friendly. The recommendation was for the government to establish a bond or a kitty that provides incentives. Besides getting people to invest more in sustainable practices such as solar panels for energy, the government should help people to start actively thinking about sustainability and equity. Without government support there is little impetus to consider environmental sustainability when investing. However, the tax regime required even for climate friendly taxes is high and prohibitive. As government tries to shore up taxes to deal with the debt crisis, formerly zero-rated climate friendly equipment now attracts excise duty. For instance, participants pointed out that material needed for solar power is heavily taxed by the government yet this could offer better alternative to the current overreliance of electricity. Heavy taxation discourages business enterprises from setting up and adopting sustainable practices. By offering incentives for investments that promote sustainability, the government can help citizens pursue sustainable practise. This could be through incentives like tax rebates.

Participation

Through Articles 10 and 118 of the Constitution of Kenya, the Government of Kenya is mandated to incorporate public participation in processes of policy development. However, this is process is often overlooked. Hence even in plans and processes of climate change and sustainability public participation is not carried out and when it is, it barely meets the thresholds and standards envisioned in the Constitution. Participation is often carried out with few people, often those already involved in the policy processes leaving out populations that actually bear the worst effects of climate change. Environmental and sustainability policy process spaces are closed, elitist and esoteric with little room for ordinary citizens. Exclusion from participation in itself is a form of participatory inequity. The result of a lack of participation, is a lack of awareness of policies and laws on matters that guide environmental law and processes. Government officials participating in the study acknowledged the need to prioritize citizen participation and provide information on policies, strategies and plans on sustainability and climate change. Lack of involvement and participation leads to a lack of ownership and responsibility, further undermining collective action towards sustainability. Participants in the study expressed that though they feel and see the impact of environmental degradation and the need for sustainable practices they feel little responsibility to address the issues. A lack of resources to address the environmental degradation makes them powerless hence they leave the responsibility therefore to government. Government administration was of the opinion that even when invited citizens fail to show up

unless they have been directly impacted. Community participation and citizen empowerment at policy processes remains low resulting in little action on environmental sustainability.

Reactive measures

Emerging from the discussions is that most efforts at sustainability whether by the community or by government itself are mostly reactive. In discussions participants mentioned how for instance when flooding happened in the area, the government and community members could have undertaken prior measures to prevent loss of life and destruction of property. There was general agreement that there is little planning by government and communities on how to handle the effects of environmental degradation like flooding, and that efforts are often reactive after the climate catastrophe has occurred.

While innovation was discussed as key to promoting proactive measures, the education system lacks this as part of its curriculum. According to participants the education system is rigid and does not encourage thinking around innovative measures to curb environmental degradation and measures to promote sustainability.

Globalization and the need for growth

For a developing country like Kenya, the balance between securing livelihoods and adopting environmentally sustainable practices is challenging. Most actions to secure people's livelihood are sometimes in contradiction to aspects of sustainability. National developments like industrialization can compromise the environment and sustainability. In low-income countries like Kenya, industrialization is desirable for among many reasons the creation of employment to the large youth population in need of livelihood options. Governments have an arduous task to balance industrialization, create jobs for the huge youthful population and at the same time ensure that factories set up adhere to environmentally sustainable procedures.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

NATIONAL AND LOCAL LEVEL

- The national administration must enhance proactive participation of citizens in discussions, forums and policy processes on environmental sustainability. Adherence to constitutional provisions related to public participation at all levels – local to national – should be improved to ensure inclusion and voice of citizens. Participation will foster collective action, enhance ownership and responsibility on environmental sustainability.
- The government should put in place an incentive structure for activities and mechanisms that promote sustainable environmental practices for individuals and businesses. For instance, the government could, for instance, reduce or exempt taxation on imported materials that enhance environmental sustainability. Such incentives would enable increased uptake of sustainable alternatives for businesses and households.
- To promote equity, government should improve access to basic services through universal provisions that do not require out-of-pocket user payments. In a context of precarious jobs and livelihood options, the commodification of basic services harms the poor and vulnerable most. Universal social services, including social protection, would secure livelihoods, and, furthermore, enhance equity.

INTERNATIONAL LEVEL

- At the global level, agreements related to climate justice need to be implemented to support governments in the Global South to help them address the effects of climate change.

5.1.2. Pakistan

In Pakistan the participatory workshops conducted using the *Le Grand Jeu (LGJ)* and post-game group discussions were designed to engage diverse stakeholders in exploring Pakistan’s green transition. There was representation from all four provinces (Punjab, Sindh, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Balochistan) and the capital (Islamabad Federal Capital Territory). The workshops aimed to capture their perspectives on the aspirations, challenges, and policy solutions necessary for a sustainable future. Thus, an important characteristic of the the workshops in Pakistan was that they by design placed an emphasis on regional diversity and variation.

The research team used a simplified script based on the scenario from the SPES *Le Grand Jeu (LGJ)* manual. Participants were introduced to a mid-sized city comprising urban, rural, and off-grid zones and asked to imagine themselves as settlers working to establish a sustainable society. To contextualise the scenario the game master introduced themes such as electricity shortages, urban congestion, and rural man-made disasters. The framing centred on collective survival within boundaries, using local metaphors - such as climate-induced migration, community solar projects, and local water harvesting to enhance relatability.

The workshops yielded comprehensive insights as participants identified several cross-cutting themes that reflect both shared aspirations and persistent challenges. Table 3 provides a succinct overview of the topics that emerged which are further detailed below.

Table 3: Summary of findings in Pakistan

THEME	ASPIRATIONS (DESIRABLE FUTURES & COLLECTIVE GOALS)	PROBLEMS (BARRIERS & CHALLENGES IN THE TRANSITION)	POLICY PRIORITIES AND IDEAS	ACTORS (PERCEIVED RELEVANT ACTORS AND THEIR ROLES)	COMMENT
Energy independence	100 per cent renewable utilization Energy security	Policy instability Grid limitations High costs	Feed-in tariffs Grid upgrades Decentralized solutions	National Electric Power Regulatory Authority, provincial energy departments, private investors	Disconnect between federal targets and provincial implementation
Climate resilience	Climate-proof infrastructure, Food security	Cyclical climate-economic crises Funding gaps	Early warning systems Adaptive agriculture	National and provincial disaster management authorities	Needs integration with poverty alleviation
Equitable development	Poverty reduction, gender inclusion	Informal economy vulnerabilities Rural-urban gaps	Social safety nets Skills programmes	Benazir Income Support Program Women's development departments	Cross-sectoral coordination essential

Environmental stewardship	10 per cent forest cover Pollution control	Weak enforcement Industrial pressures	Stricter regulations Ecosystem restoration	Environmental Protection Agency Forest departments	Requires judicial system engagement
Technological innovation	Smart infrastructure Local manufacturing	Financing barriers Technical skills deficit	R&D incentives Vocational training	Higher Education Commission Tech startups	Potential for youth employment

Secure and renewable energy future

Participants in the Pakistani workshops united around a clear, universal commitment to a green energy transition. One of the future visions was an energy-secure Pakistan powered by renewable sources, particularly solar and wind, to reduce the current 60 per cent dependence on imported fossil fuels. This commitment was linked to a vast untapped potential of solar and wind power, and the recognition of energy independence as a national priority. Participants noted that all provinces each with their own unique geographical advantages (Punjab's biomass, Sindh's wind corridors, KP's hydropower, Balochistan's solar, Islamabad's urban solar), aim to increase their renewable energy share to reduce reliance on imported fossil fuels and address the pressing issues of load shedding and high electricity costs. Participants further highlighted the potential of developing decentralized solutions like rooftop solar energy for rural electrification, something which could bring further improvements to those rural areas where access is still a challenge. The common challenge faced by all, however, is the impact of policy inconsistencies, grid limitations, and financing constraints which hinder the full realization of these ambitious goals and deter private investment.

Preparedness and climate resilience

Participants were also concerned about *climate resilience* and *equitable development* and they emphasised the importance of halting environmental degradation that they felt had gone too far. However, there was also an acknowledgement of a trade-off between the ecological and economic gains. One of the workshops witnessed debates over how much environmental degradation should be allowed in exchange for industrial productivity.

When it comes to climate resilience, participants noted that all provinces are grappling with significant vulnerabilities to climate-induced disasters, necessitating adaptive strategies. Punjab and Sindh face threats from floods and heatwaves, leading to initiatives in climate-smart agriculture and urban flood management. Sindh also contends with coastal erosion and saltwater intrusion, prompting mangrove restoration efforts, while KP is prone to landslides and flash floods, focusing on reforestation and early warning systems. Balochistan, on the other hand, is uniquely challenged by severe water scarcity and prolonged droughts, emphasizing water conservation. Despite these varied specific threats, the underlying similarity is the cyclical relationship between climate impacts and economic capacity, where disasters erode the ability to invest in resilience, creating a persistent crisis.

Inclusive development

Regarding equitable development, all provinces share the overarching challenge of socioeconomic disparities, with significant portions of their populations living below the poverty line and lacking access to essential services. Rural-urban divides in access to education, healthcare, and infrastructure are a common theme across Punjab, Sindh, KP, and Balochistan, with Islamabad also having pockets of inequality. The pervasive issue of the informal economy leaving a large population without social safety nets makes them acutely vulnerable to climate shocks and economic downturns across the board. Efforts to address these include skill development, microfinance, and specific programmes targeting women and marginalized communities, highlighting a shared understanding that inclusive policies are vital for a sustainable green transition.

Technological innovation and environmental stewardship

In environmental stewardship and technological innovation, the workshop discussions revealed shared concerns across the provinces but to some extent tailored regional approaches. All provinces are battling environmental degradation through deforestation, water scarcity, land degradation, and pollution, recognizing the need for stricter regulations and ecosystem restoration. Simultaneously, there's a collective push towards adopting climate-friendly technologies like precision agriculture, electric vehicles, and waste-to-energy solutions to enhance resource efficiency and reduce emissions. While Punjab leads in agri-drones and biogas, Sindh in wind/solar technologies, KP in micro-hydropower and deforestation monitoring, and Balochistan in solar-powered water solutions, the common thread is the recognition of financing barriers, technical skill deficits, and the need for local manufacturing to fully leverage these innovations for a greener and more resilient Pakistan.

Overall, the core implication for Pakistan's green transition is the urgent need for a holistic, integrated strategy that transcends fragmented approaches. This means establishing a stable and coordinated national policy framework to unlock massive renewable energy potential, breaking the vicious cycle of climate-induced economic vulnerability through strategic, resilience-building investments, and ensuring a truly just transition by actively including and empowering marginalized communities.

General observations

The findings from the participatory workshops highlight a critical tension at the heart of Pakistan's green transition: the urgent imperative for sustainable development clashes significantly with existing environmental constraints and systemic challenges. This mirrors the broader national policy dilemmas evident in documents like the National Climate Change Policy (2021) and the Alternative and Renewable Energy Policy (2019). While participants articulated a clear vision for an energy-secure, climate-resilient, and equitable Pakistan, the dialogue consistently returned to the persistent implementation gaps and bureaucratic hurdles identified throughout the workshops.

The workshops also brought to light critical insights into energy access and rural electrification. Despite the promise of decentralized renewable solutions (solar home systems, mini-grids, micro-hydropower) for connecting the 30 per cent of the rural population lacking electricity, their adoption is hindered by the lack of targeted policies and significant financing barriers. While provincial governments are making strides in areas like Sindh's wind corridors or KP's micro-hydropower projects, a unified national strategy is critical to streamline permitting, ensure community engagement, and develop local capacity for installation and maintenance. The role of international donors (World Bank, ADB etc.) was acknowledged for their financial and technical support, though

some participants cautioned against over-reliance, advocating for increased domestic resource mobilization.

Ultimately, the workshops conclusively demonstrated that Pakistan's green transition is a multi-faceted challenge. It demands an integrated policymaking approach that simultaneously addresses energy poverty, enhances climate adaptation, and reduces inequality. This integration must leverage technological innovation, actively bridge federal-provincial divides, and prioritize the protection and empowerment of vulnerable populations to ensure a truly just and sustainable future.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

PROVINCIAL AND LOCAL LEVEL

- Workshop discussions highlighted the importance of implementing integrated urban-rural resilience plans, combining green infrastructure (Islamabad's permeable pavements model) with decentralized energy solutions (Sindh's mini-grid approach), enforced through updated building codes.

NATIONAL LEVEL

- There is a need for provincial climate innovation funds with mandatory 30 per cent allocation for community-led renewable projects, coupled with streamlined federal-provincial coordination mechanisms to accelerate the 30 per cent renewables target by 2030.

GLOBAL LEVEL

- A South-South climate technology transfer facility should be set up under UNFCCC, prioritizing affordable smart grid solutions and drought-resistant crop technologies for vulnerable regions like Balochistan.

5.1.3. Sri Lanka

In the SPES *Le Grand Jeu (LGJ)* game in Sri Lanka, players were invited to play a game in which the aim was to work towards creating a society that they individually would consider as the ideal society. Two grids represented the physical world consisting of a rural and an urban area separated by a river. There was no easy crossing close by, and the closest bridge was 10 kms away. The urban area was already equipped with basic services (hospital, bank, school, governmental institutions) and infrastructure (electricity, water, sewers, internet, roads). The rural area had fewer resources and was less developed. Players could also settle off the grid where there were no taxes but also no public services or infrastructure. Table 4 provides an overview of the findings in Sri Lanka.

Table 4: Summary of findings in Sri Lanka

THEME	ASPIRATIONS (DESIRABLE FUTURES & COLLECTIVE GOALS)	PROBLEMS (BARRIERS & CHALLENGES IN THE TRANSITION)	POLICY PRIORITIES AND IDEAS	ACTORS (PERCEIVED RELEVANT ACTORS AND THEIR ROLES)
Living standards as priority	Economic development of rural areas and livelihoods (esp. in farming but also off farm)	Lack of economic activity in rural areas, the need for government intervention to assist farmers, in emergencies, extreme weather events etc	Business development and private sector development in rural area. Reduction of government transfers which create dependency	Government Civil society
Equity	Socially conscious societies where individuals look out for each other and everyone has their basic needs met	Not everyone values or recognizes the importance of equity		
Role of government and its capacity	Effective implementation of environmental policies, incentives for engaging in greening and penalties for pollution	Government does not have the capacity to implement policies Agencies tasked with implementation do not have the capacity, resources or power to implement Attitudes of policymakers which relegate environmental	Strengthen the agencies tasked with implementing environmental policies through budgetary support, personnel and institutional capacity Foster transformative attitudinal change at the top, as well as among individuals	Individual policymakers esp. at the top Environmental agencies Civil society Individuals

		concerns to the bottom		
Change in farming practices	Farmers use less fertilizer and pesticides, more availability of organic produce	Farmers are thinking of their bottom line and don't have the economic resources to engage in organic farming, which is more costly and also more risky	Innovation and government support	Farmers, Government, Consumers
Responsibility and scale	Big polluters, at the level of the country and globally, are reined in	Individual change will require major changes in habits and behaviour, but will make little difference unless big polluters, both locally and internationally stop / reduce pollution	Setting up of regional and international spaces where pressure can be exerted to demand change	Government Civil society organisations, Regional forums, International forums
Living standards as priority	Economic development of rural areas and livelihoods (esp in farming but also off farm)	Lack of economic activity in rural areas, the need for government intervention to assist farmers, in emergencies, extreme weather events etc	Business development and private sector development in rural area. Reduction of government transfers which create dependency	Government Civil society
Change in social attitudes	Change in the way we look at the environment, to value it	Everything is monetised. production orientation, competition, busy lives		
Understanding climate change	Recognize and accept man-made climate change as a phenomenon	While some people (urban, educated etc) are well versed on the concept, others see this as irregular patterns of rain, drought, or as something that humans cannot affect by our behaviour.		

Higher living standards

In all three games, players prioritized the need to ensure acceptable living standards in terms of access to infrastructure and income sources. There was an implied as well as explicit acceptance that improving lifestyles is a priority over all else.

"(During the game) we were only interested in our own progress" (g3, p1)

Some of the players were self-conscious and appeared to feel that this is not something they should prioritize but still did it.

"If I have land, I would like to go organic and be self-sufficient. At the same time, the urban area has more facilities. So, I would like to have those conveniences and be in my comfort zone" (g1, p3).

Two female players noted that while their aspirations tended towards off-grid and rural, when deciding where to settle both opted to place at least one urban piece of land for security reasons:

"I prefer to be in the forest area. However, in reality, I need security as a female. So, I will live in the rural village. But I also need a location in the city for business. Because the markets are not very lucrative in the village and the better markets are in the urban setting" (g1, p1)

In contrast, there were other players who openly prioritized production and income over the environment:

"We have to clear the jungle and cut trees to start a chena cultivation. It is impossible to prevent environmental damage. We cannot remove the damage 100 per cent." (g3, p2).

In the post-game discussions, players noted that there is a socially enforced focus on productive activities and income generation.

"The world is driven by production and the rest is less important. Everyone is in competition to do better than their neighbours. All 20 million in Sri Lanka want to get to that high level of income and consumption. Is that sustainable? But those are their aspirations." (g2, p1)

In all three games, players discussed the apparent inverse relationship between production activities, on the one hand, and environmental sustainability, on the other. They felt that conscious decision-making was needed to find the balance and the game was useful in this regard.

"I wish that real society could be more like the one in the game we played. The ideal is if we can make conscious decisions like we did in the game. For instance, if we can think about reducing the environmental pollution, have collaboration among people, and have better attitudes towards a sustainable society. Although it was an imaginary society, it helped us to think that we should not harm anyone when we are gearing towards our own success" (g3, p2)

Equity and basic needs satisfaction

Players expressed an aspiration for a socially conscious society where individuals look out for each other, and everyone has their basic needs met.

"When I think of an ideal world, I think along the lines of decent jobs, respect, reducing inequality." (g2, p3)

In all three games, players felt that there is a certain threshold and if anyone is falling below that it is the shared responsibility of the government and society, to help. During the games, players showed willingness to complement the state, with individual or community contributions to support persons in need. In this regard, players reasoned that in their games as well as in the larger Sri Lankan society there is a much greater orientation towards promoting equity by providing basic necessities than towards protecting the environment. They wondered if this was a cultural tendency stemming from our history as a welfare-oriented state. At the same time, some were sceptical players objected to what they saw as a handout culture and noted that the government should not provide unconditional social assistance.

Players were also conscious that equity is not a priority for many, especially in the private sector.

"When we think of designing a future, there is a mismatch that comes from the private sector. I find it difficult to convince them on equity. Our individual backgrounds play such an important role in our decisions and the game brought that out well." (g2, p3)

Ecological choices versus economic profit in farming

Players in urban areas articulated an aspiration for less use of harmful fertilizer and pesticides in farming and a greater availability and accessibility of organic produce. At the same time, they also recognized the difficulties of engaging in organic farming as a livelihood, and either supplemented their organic farm with a non-organic farm or engaged in limited organic cultivation for own consumption. In the post-game discussion, players in urban areas noted that many farmers did the same thing:

"I think that in the real world, people are selfish. For instance, I have seen so many farmers who grow rice paddy without fertilizer for their home consumption. But for selling and making profits they use fertilizer." (g1, p1)

In Game 3 which was played in a farming community, none of the players decided to engage in organic farming. This is despite the widespread prevalence of kidney disease associated with pesticide and fertilizer run off mixing with water sources in the area. Instead, one player decided to engage in purifying and selling drinking water to the community, which is a profitable activity in the Dry Zone. This reflects the perception in the eyes of both the farmers and the consumers, that overuse of chemicals in farming is connected more closely with health concerns than environmental degradation.

Weaknesses in policy coordination and implementation

Across the workshops, implementation was highlighted as a key obstacle to progress towards a more sustainable society. While there is no lack of relevant laws and regulations on paper, these are often not implemented and enforced. There is patchy implementation which is affected by political interference, lack of interest among bureaucrats and the sheer complexity of government operations. In the absence of external coercion, through enforcement of penalties for

environmental violations, individuals are unlikely to change their behaviour. Few people are taking climate action out of conviction, but the majority must be compelled or incentivized.

Players identified several causal factors in this context. Firstly, the government apparatus is structured as multiple entities with overlapping responsibilities and fail to ensure enough coordination across the system. Each ministry and government agency develops policies relevant to their mandate and to address issues they are facing. Project-based development activities add to this confusion as they are developed to address specific issues. This results in a tendency for agencies to operate in isolation, engaging in piece-meal policymaking that are not a coherent and consistent, often neglecting “the big picture”.

Another causal factor identified by the players is that agencies tasked with protecting the environment are usually less powerful compared to those in charge of production, and lack the teeth to enforce environmental laws, regulations and policies. Players noted that when penalties for flagrant environmental damage are not properly implemented, the ability of these entities to act meaningfully on behalf of sustainable development is limited.

Finally, the players identified the mindset of bureaucrats and policy implementers, who do not sufficiently value the environment and regularly prioritise economic growth even at the cost of massive environmental damage. Rather than aspiring to be more like countries with high levels of development, infrastructure and living standards, one player suggested that we should aspire to be more like countries successfully pursuing sustainable development models. “Why can’t we be more like Costa Rica?” she wondered (g2, p1).

Division of responsibility and collective action challenges

Players noted Sri Lanka’s relatively insignificant contribution to climate change. Some players felt that as individuals and as a country, they could do very little.

“We may be able to address issues locally, but we do not have the voice to control other countries. Other countries pollute on far large scales. In a global sense Sri Lanka has almost zero impact on climate change.” (g2, p1)

As a medium sized island nation which is well integrated into the global economy, players felt that options available to Sri Lanka were restricted in ways that the game did not capture. As a country, Sri Lanka is engaged in international economic competition and the aspirations of Sri Lankans, such as a strong consumerist orientation, are shaped by global forces such as the media, both mainstream and social media.

Feeling helpless against global forces, players operated on a smaller scale and addressed the local level and their immediate environment. In the third workshop that took place in a rural region, players were concerned about the environmental degradation in and around their local lake, which is used for bathing, household needs and farming. During the post-game discussion as well as during post-game interviews, players brainstormed ideas to address this local level pollution.

In general, during the workshops, participants noted the contrast between the game and real life. In the game their attitudes had been aligned, and it was easy to resolve disputes through discussion. By contrast, in real life there are many who are focused on their own advancement at the expense of everything else. In both urban and rural areas, players pointed to the pervasive competitiveness that children and adults face at school and work. As a result, many people do not have the time or the inclination to reflect and be thoughtful about their actions. They recognised that time is the most valuable commodity, but it is in short supply for most people.

Further, many people are discouraged from taking climate action because these activities all reduce life’s conveniences, takes up precious time and can also be costly. In addition, returns on

mitigation efforts often have a time lag and benefits are not always visible at the individual level. As with countries, individuals are discouraged when the biggest polluters continue to pollute while those who have a small carbon footprint to begin with, incur expenditure and inconvenience and disproportionate considering their modest level of greenhouse gas emissions. In this context, changing social attitudes to voluntarily adopt climate action is an uphill battle.

Knowledge, awareness and climate discourses

Both the game and the post-game discussion show that in Sri Lanka, there are different understandings of sustainable development, climate change and the need for a green transition. These are linked to people's levels of education, livelihood, their place of residence and lived experience.

In the two workshops organised in urban areas, the players discussed the need for mitigation and attempted to incorporate mitigation measures into their production activities. Several players in the urban groups installed solar panels on their roofs, expressed a desire to engage in organic farming and to maintain some of their lands as forests. By contrast, in the game played in rural Medawachchiya, the players were largely unfamiliar with the global climate change discourse. They explained that while some changes in weather patterns have been noticed, there is no single explanation for these changes.

"(p)people in our village do not discuss it. There are farmer societies, but this is not something that they discuss. We notice that there is a change in the rainy season and the harvesting season but it is not seen as part of a single larger phenomenon" (g3, p2)

It may be possible that farmers are experiencing and making sense of climate change using different terminology.

"People just get adjusted to the different changes in the weather. They may say it's the gods, or their karma, or they may say that it's nature's reaction to the way we are treating nature" (g3, p2)

Trees were not valued as a mitigation measure and their conservation was not particularly prioritized. As chena cultivators all the players in the third workshop agreed that there is nothing inherently bad, in cutting down trees.

In the post-game discussions, therefore, players discussed the need adapt the climate change discourse to make it more relevant for the local population as well as to incorporate their understanding into the country level response. Too much reliance on scientific terms and jargon which also do not translate well into local languages, makes the climate change discourse alien to local communities.

"The conversation does not reach them. They do not know the issues, neither do they have any interest in policy conversations. The policy focus is not their focus, unless it is made relevant to their day-to-day life. Macro level policy conversations are dominated by experts and not the vulnerable groups. Even if there is a chance to engage, they will be disregarded. In particular indigenous communities are excluded in these policy conversations" (g2, p5)

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

NATIONAL AND GLOBAL LEVELS

- State authorities responsible for safeguarding the environment should be given greater power to implement existing policies and enforce penalties on those who cause environmental damage.
- Participants identified a scale issue related to Sri Lanka's role as a small contributor to global emissions. They felt that climate action at country level was meaningless in the face of continuing emissions by big polluters on the global stage.
- The urgency to act on behalf of the climate is not yet at the forefront in the minds of the general public in Sri Lanka. Changes are required to the climate change discourse in the country to make it more inclusive and localised, in terms of both language and concepts.

5.2. Europe

5.2.1. Hungary

The starting point of the LGJ sessions in Hungary was that players were invited to rebuild a recently flooded city in which only a few basic services (hospital, bank, school, governmental and city hall) and infrastructure (electricity, water, sewage, gas, internet, roads) remained. A thematic analysis of the output from the workshops in Hungary, led to the identification of seven themes. We link these to the dimensions of aspirations or collective goals, key transition barriers and transition policy priorities and ideas. Table 5 provides a summary of the findings which we further elaborate on below.

Table 5: Summary of findings in Hungary

THEME	ASPIRATIONS OR COLLECTIVE GOALS	KEY CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS	POLICY PRIORITIES AND IDEAS	RELEVANT ACTORS AND THEIR ROLES	COMMENT
Value system and cultural norms	Environmental and social justice “Enough” instead of continuous growth	Current societal values prioritize economic growth and profit	Integrate social justice dimensions in policy design	Central government: set frameworks Educational institutions: shape values Civil society: advocacy	Reflects normative debates around what “sustainability” should cover
Participation and empowerment	More equal bargaining power among actors Inclusive planning processes Communities can pressure decision-makers and shape sustainability trajectories	Power asymmetries (e.g., investors, state) hinder fair negotiations Some actors (e.g., rural populations) lack basic services services and channels of participation Insufficient cross-sectoral dialogue Societal fragmentation and lack of cooperation between social groups	Empower local actors via education Rebalance development focus towards human and natural capital Facilitate platforms for dialogue Support local involvement and deliberation processes	Central government: regulation and funding to diversify power Local governments and municipalities: planning Investors: engagement Marginalized groups: empowerment Civil society	The game allowed for more balanced interaction than real life, exposing this gap
Education and awareness	Informed, critical, and creative citizens able to contribute to sustainability	Sustainability is not sufficiently discussed Public poorly informed Climate literacy low	Integrate sustainability into all levels of education Promote lifelong learning Use more innovative tools to promote	Educational institutions Media NGOs Government (curriculum policy)	A broad societal understanding of sustainability is still emerging

THEME	ASPIRATIONS OR COLLECTIVE GOALS	KEY CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS	POLICY PRIORITIES AND IDEAS	RELEVANT ACTORS AND THEIR ROLES	COMMENT
			sustainability education		
Economic system	Shift from low-skill, exploitative industrial models to R&D and green innovation with highly skilled and creative jobs	Domestic economy relies on low-skilled cheap labour Job creation often prioritized over ecological impact and to invest in social development	Incentives to promote sustainability in industry Support R&D and startups Promote geothermal and other renewables; revise labour laws	National government (incentives, tax policy) Private sector EU (funding and oversight)	Shift from extractive to regenerative economic logic needed
Governance and institutional design	Transparent, inclusive institutions Central coordination of sustainability policy	Weak coordination between government levels No independent environmental ministry Fragmented strategies	Reinstatement of the environmental ministry Foster participation of local communities and via new technologies	National government (coordination) Local authorities (implementation) Citizens (participation)	Institutional fragmentation is seen as a bottleneck
Infrastructure and planning	Inclusive planning of urban and rural development and transport	Lack of basic services in rural areas and infrastructure Centralized decisions often ignore local needs	Empower local authorities Co-create infrastructure plans with residents Address transport poverty	Local governments Urban planners Community groups National development agencies	Urban-rural divide intensifies spatial sustainability differences
Environmental degradation and pollution	Cleaner environment	Daily impacts of pollution are not sufficiently recognized; unnecessary emissions debated (e.g., flying); insufficient green infrastructure	Better waste management and waste reduction (e.g., more packaging-free shops) Expanding geothermal and renewables use	Environmental agencies Municipalities Citizens Businesses	Points to both technical and behavioural levers

While the participants in Hungary expressed numerous aspirations for a more sustainable and equitable future, the workshop discussions were dominated by the key challenges and barriers to sustainability – in Hungary, more broadly in the EU and at a global scale. As reflected in Table 5, participants identified numerous systemic and societal barriers that hinder progress toward social,

economic and environmental sustainability in Hungary. These included practical, structural, and cultural limitations that constrain environmental, social, and economic progress.

Future visions

The vision for the future expressed by participants centred around environmental sustainability from the aspects of inclusiveness, critical reflection on existing paradigms of growth and economic goals, and a holistic approach that balances social, ecological, and economic sustainability. Empowering citizens—especially marginalized groups—and embedding sustainability in cultural and educational narratives were seen as fundamental to achieving these aspirations. Participants advocated for a more future-oriented mindset, one where people are encouraged and enabled to think long-term. A recurring theme was the need to redefine the values underpinning modern society. Some participants proposed shifting the core value system towards “humanity itself,” rather than material or economic metrics. This shift would entail reconsidering the goals of sustainable development to emphasize the reduction of inequalities and the introduction of the concept of “enough,” challenging the prevailing ideology of everlasting improvement.

Participation and empowerment

One of the most prominent observations was the discrepancy in the articulation and consideration of diverse interests and standpoints, especially when considering the contrast between game-life and real-life. While participants found it relatively easy and effective to engage in constructive dialogue and fair negotiation during the board game, they emphasized that such communication rarely functions effectively in real-life settings. The game allowed for a levelling of bargaining power among participants, which is considered as an ideal situation that sharply contrasted with societal realities, where power asymmetries often undermine collaborative sustainability efforts.

A related insight emerging from the sessions was the emphasis on bottom-up approaches. Participants observed that when individuals or communities are involved in the decision-making process, they are more likely to feel a sense of ownership and responsibility for the outcomes. However, in Hungary social groups do not naturally view each other as partners in addressing systemic challenges, leading to fragmented efforts and reduced efficiency in sustainability interventions. In general, it was widely considered that local residents do not have sufficient opportunities and resources of any type that might be relevant. Thus, they are not used to participate in local affairs.

Furthermore, female empowerment emerged as an aspiration highlighted by a player in one of the games. In this game there was a contrast in how men and women approached sustainability. Female participants were more inclined toward small-scale, community-oriented ecological investments, while men favoured larger-scale, technocratic solutions. Even if this observation featured in only one of the games, it arguably points to the importance of women's empowerment in future sustainability efforts.

Cooperation and early-stage planning were also emphasized as essential for realizing sustainable futures. One player reflected that pre-game discussions about shared goals would have led to more coherent city planning, which was accepted by the others and thus the game followed a cooperative approach with coordinated actions. This experience illustrated the need for participatory processes during the early stages of infrastructure or urban development projects.

Trade-offs between social and economic priorities and ecological costs

Economic sustainability was another issue that participants felt is not sufficiently addressed in the public debate. Several participants noted that the average citizen rarely considers the balance between economic rationality and environmental impact in daily life. In addition, economic interests often conflict with environmental objectives. Examples include trade-offs between job creation through factory development and environmental degradation, or the prioritization of economic growth even when it entails significant ecological costs. These tensions are compounded in rural contexts, where basic services such as grocery stores are often lacking, pushing sustainability far down the priority list. Moreover, even if saving, recycling, and waste minimisation are traditional rural norms that still exist to some extent today, some of these sustainable practices might also have harmful impacts to the environment in poorer households (e.g. due to expensive heating fuels, many household waste products are burned, the smoke from which can be polluting).

Ecological sustainability in a broader sense is often perceived as a luxury relative to immediate socioeconomic needs. Socioeconomic inequalities were also relevant in this context, including the unbalanced distribution of state support (e.g., subsidies favouring the wealthy), and the minimal attention given to the everyday impact of pollution and environmental degradation. Several participants also pointed to the nature of the capitalist system itself as a problem. Its emphasis on continual growth, was identified as a structural obstacle to sustainability. There was also a critical awareness of the superficial treatment of sustainability by political actors, who were perceived as more interested in growth and electoral gains than in genuine ecological transitions.

At the same time, it is important to note that some participants pointed out a particular feature in the game. The influence of socially conscious opinion leaders in the game led to a strong emphasis on social justice at the expense of economic sustainability. This imbalance, they noted, mirrors real-world political dynamics in which elite discourses can alienate segments of the population, potentially leading to populist backlashes.

Policy ideas for the sustainability transition

Participants identified a variety of policy directions and priorities that could potentially advance sustainability in both urban and rural Hungarian contexts. Improving education should be a key priority. Sustainability must be integrated across educational levels, starting from citizenship education and extending into higher education and beyond. Educational policies should also promote awareness and creativity that could contribute to innovative solutions to sustainability challenges. The board game itself was seen as an example for a valuable educational tool and a lesson that such innovative tools should be incorporated more widely into formal and informal education systems. Another key suggestion was to address transport poverty and to develop infrastructure in ways that empower communities to allow them to exercise their bargaining power, including on environmental issues.

The board game also highlighted the importance of policy levers at multiple levels of governance. While central government was viewed as capable of pushing big companies toward sustainable practices, local governments were seen as critical actors for initiating and implementing solutions tailored to community needs. This multi-level governance approach reflects the subtle distinction between how top-down and bottom-up approaches should complement each other, which participants generally felt was not working well enough in Hungary.

In conclusion, participants perceived education and public awareness as the cornerstone of sustainability transitions. They emphasized the urgency of pursuing green policy changes and awareness-raising efforts simultaneously, as there is no time for one to lag behind the other.

Achieving sustainability requires structural reform, a shift in societal values, and inclusive governance mechanisms that bridge the gap between policy intent and lived reality.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

NATIONAL LEVEL

- Participants emphasized the need for greater policy coherence and accountability, particularly from central government actors, whom they felt should play a more active role in regulating and incentivizing sustainable development.
- Local agency and collective pressure – from communities and municipalities – are important in shaping investment decisions and demanding socially just and environmentally sound outcomes.
- Sustainability governance must be strengthened through clear and enforceable regulation, targeted incentives, and equitable development policies, especially in regions facing depopulation or basic service deficits.

EUROPEAN LEVEL

- Frameworks should much better address the structural imbalances among member states and support just transitions that are sensitive to local needs and capacities.

5.2.2. Italy

This section details the results from the Italian workshops, which, through the creation of a desirable society, were designed to elicit insights into participants' perceptions of sustainability in both local and national contexts, fostering discussions around key social, environmental, and economic challenges. In Table 6, which summarises the Italian findings, we organise the output in five broad themes. An issue that cuts across the themes in Table 6 is that of social fairness and inclusion, giving opportunities particularly for the most vulnerable and avoiding placing the costs of the sustainability transition on the least well-off. In Italy there was no extensive discussion on the different actors most relevant for the sustainability transition and the processes of policymaking. However, it is worth highlighting the key role of civil society plays in fostering collective responsibility and mobilising awareness.

Table 6: Summary of findings in Italy

THEME	ASPIRATIONS OR COLLECTIVE GOALS	KEY CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS	POLICY PRIORITIES AND IDEAS
Nature-quality of life nexus	Improved quality of life with stronger connections between nature and community	Lack of collective responsibility Tension between nature as collective good and private property rights Exclusionary ownership and access to the countryside and nature Tension between need for renewable energy and costs for nature	Give people more time to spend outdoors Involvement of affected local communities in decisions about renewable energy production Protection of biodiversity
Social wellbeing and inequality	Inclusion and belonging for everyone Social cohesion	Spatial inequalities and scarcity of public transport outside the cities Inequality in access to information technology Job losses from technological change (e.g., robotization)	Public goods redefined as common goods Redistribution of jobs Creation of green jobs
Education	Quality education for all	Education system is underfunded and detached from real world issues	Enhance knowledge and awareness Increase investments in education and research
Economic system and the environment	Ecologically sustainable economic system	Unsustainable production Overconsumption Energy-intensity of the economy	Consume less Stronger regulations but avoiding a disproportionate

THEME	ASPIRATIONS OR COLLECTIVE GOALS	KEY CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS	POLICY PRIORITIES AND IDEAS
			burden on socially vulnerable persons Shorter or more flexible workweek
Accountability and participation	Politically legitimate and accountable policymaking Effective but socially fair transition policies Solidarity	Mistrust in institutions Inefficiency and inaction of governing institutions Tension between urgency of environmental action and inclusive decision-making Power imbalance between economic elites and ordinary people	More space for bottom-up grassroots initiatives Community-based solutions Make formal institutions more responsive

Access to nature, wellbeing and social inclusion

Participants expressed aspirations for a better quality of life rooted in a deep connection to nature, community, and shared wellbeing. Nature was not viewed as separate from humans but as an integral part of life, shaping both personal fulfilment and collective responsibility.

Similarly, a shared vision of wellbeing rooted in balance, mutual respect, and collective inclusion emerged from the workshops. Social value was described as the ability to achieve personal wellbeing without undermining others' opportunities.

"[...] In this case, there is a high social value, meaning if I manage to satisfy what is my well-being, which is quite subjective, without taking too much away from those around me, there's a high social value in my opinion." (g1_p3_student)

"[...] more dialogue between us – that alone is a social value, isn't it?" (g3_p3_op)

The importance of emotional safety and social connection emerged, with participants highlighting the value of small towns and community-oriented neighbourhoods.

"Cities dehumanise people... we need to carve out space—a green space—for our mental health." (g3_p1_op)

Public good was redefined as "common good"—shared, co-managed resources rather than delegated services. Some acknowledged that infrastructure contributes to the quality of life but emphasised that wellbeing is also social.

"We have a common vision [...] Social cohesion, space for everyone, the possibility of finding a place to belong, the fact that there's still this feeling of inclusion... that's what allowed us to give it more value." (g2_p1_op)

As far as barriers to the realisation of this ideal vision, ownership and control over natural or semi-natural spaces emerged as a contested issue, revealing tensions between collective value and

private claims. Outside the game, the logic of shared responsibility often fades, obscured by social, economic, or emotional barriers that make it difficult to sustain collective action.

"[...] I bought a house [...]" (g3_p1_op) "Yes, but remember where you are." (g3_p3_op) "You're on planet Terra di Tutti." (g3_p4_op) "But I bought it, it's mine, and I'm fixing it up." (g3_p2_op)

"Anyway, the obvious thing was that when we were playing, we all clearly understood that the beans [negative externalities] were a problem for everyone, so we were all interested in helping reduce the central beans. Whereas in everyday life, the fact that the central beans – let's say, that this little pot of resources – should be reduced isn't so clear, immediate, or accessible to everyone... [...]" (g2_p2_op)

Concerns were also raised about environmental degradation tied to the placement of renewable energy plants, where green solutions themselves can become problematic when implemented without attention to local land use.

"We need to understand where these plants are also being built, on what kind of land." (g2_p2_op)

"If they then build a solar panel plant that paves over an entire area, for me it's [...]" (g2_p3_op)

Trade-off between fast environmental action and citizen participation

Participants reflected on the tension between urgent environmental action and inclusive decision-making. While some recognised the need for swift measures such as bans or restrictions, others questioned their legitimacy when imposed without public participation.

"It's a process, but at a certain point there was, let's say, a ban, right? It was decided that this could no longer be used, this could no longer be put on the market." (g3_p4_op) "And do you think that decision came from the people, from the bottom up?" (g3_p2_op)

Related to the recognition of a tension between institutional interventions and grassroots efforts, participants also highlighted the need for policies that are not only effective but socially fair. While top-down regulations were seen as potentially impactful, they should not disproportionately burden individuals, particularly those already in precarious situations:

"I want the damage to be felt by companies, not by people." (g3_p3_op)

Social inequalities and transformation of the economic system

A strong thread across the dialogues is the desire to challenge dominant models of overconsumption and unsustainable production. These reflections connect with broader critiques of production and energy use.

"The point is not to produce more energy, it's to consume less." (g1_p3_student)

"[...] incentives for families or individuals to use or make the best of the city they live in and give them the chance to spend time outdoors or have the chance to spend time, [...] So, definitely helping families have more time to use certain spaces, certain services, I don't know, by shortening the workweek or making work hours more flexible could also be an incentive." (g1_p1_student)

Participants called for a reimagining of economic systems to support a more sustainable and just society based on welfare, viewing money as the problem, but also as a potential solution.

"Money exists – it's a kind of energy [...] it can be used for good or bad" (g2_p3_op).

Power asymmetries and trust in institutions

One of the main barriers expressed by the participants was distrust of the government and the political organs at all levels which stems from negative past experiences.

"No, I don't trust that this tax is being used for renewable energy. [...] because I don't trust government orders in general. [...]" (g2_p3_op)

"I'd like to think of actors whose goal is the common good." (g1_p4_student)

This leads to power imbalances and social inequalities which emerge strongly in the interviews, particularly around the relationship between economic power and political influence.

"I would say the first thing that comes to mind is the power discrepancy between those who have money and those who don't [...] so the issue, in my opinion, is really that those with more economic power automatically have more political weight compared to those who are just ordinary people." (g1_p4_student)

The prevailing view is that those in positions of wealth and authority are not incentivised to challenge their status, which leaves ordinary citizens with limited power to influence change.

"I think there's a great deal of disillusionment with institutions, [...] I see that we all believe a bit more in grassroots initiatives. Or even in individual entrepreneurship—someone deciding to do something for the good of others—and where there's corporate responsibility. But not on a macro level—because when you go macro, all our energy just fades." (g3_p3_op)

Knowledge and education as key facilitators

Education and knowledge emerged as foundational pillars in participants' visions for a more sustainable and equitable world, starting from schools.

"Anyway, education is always fundamental; you can do it at any time, in any situation. [...]" (g3_p1_op)

"I propose that public schools in the area, both in the urban and non-urban parts, to monitor climate changes [...]" (g3_p4_op)

Participants highlighted the challenges in accessing and using information effectively to drive change. While some believed that greater awareness and education could foster collective

environmental sensitivity, others noted that information alone wasn't enough to change behaviours.

Other reflections underlined the link between education, research, media, public investment, and innovation:

"Without research, there is no solution." (g1_p3_student)

"[...] in the Italian context, research is not really used as a reference. It's hard to see it highlighted as in other contexts. So even if research is making great strides, politicians should be in the forefront, but as a knock-on effect, people should also rely more on research in many areas, including innovation. [...]."
(g1_p1_student)

Lastly, a participant stressed the need to rethink investment in education as a systemic driver of change:

"[...] But if we can increase scholarships, if we can increase access for more vulnerable people—who are often the ones experiencing the most problems and who may reason better about solutions—we need to provide some tools, let's say, for the material reasons... maybe universities and research would be more developed [...]." *(g1_p3_student)*

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

NATIONAL LEVEL

- The workshops discussions disclosed a need for investment in civic education and participatory governance mechanisms that empower communities, especially youth and marginalised groups, to shape local environmental, social and economic policies.

EUROPEAN LEVEL

- There is a need to design and implement cross-cutting policies that embed environmental justice and equity in climate action and economic planning, ensuring meaningful participation and accountability at all levels.

5.2.3. Netherlands

The four games sessions conducted in the Netherlands included a broad range of citizens with different backgrounds. Overall, they revealed a range of aspirations for building a sustainable future, as well as the obstacles participants perceived as hindering the achievement of those goals. Table 7 gives an overview of the themes that emerged in the Netherlands and how they relate to the different dimensions of interest.

Table 7: Summary of findings in the Netherlands

THEME	ASPIRATIONS OR COLLECTIVE GOALS	KEY CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS	POLICY PRIORITIES AND IDEAS	RELEVANT ACTORS AND THEIR ROLES
Nature-quality of life nexus	Balanced life where communities can live alongside and cohabit with nature Agency in decision-making	Spaces are privately owned and shaped by people who do not share the same interest in the preservation of natural habitats and the well-being of local communities	Community level decision-making Prioritize local experience in decision-making Decisions should avoid the further harming of natural habitats and reserves	Local communities and their representatives
Social wellbeing and inequality	The ability for all members of society to participate in society under more-than-sustainable living conditions	Environmental and societal problems that have been inherited from prior generations are hard to process	Create spaces for learning and collective action Redistribution of wealth and decision-making power	Policy makers who can contribute to structural change
Education	The availability of tangible and solution-oriented curriculum	People are often aware of the status quo; what is needed and desired are tangible ways to co-design an ideal future	Centres for lifelong education Research directly embedded in community spaces	Collaborations between public and private institutions
Economic system and the environment	Self-sustainability	Unpredictability of hazardous events and the cost of infrastructure	Flexible decision-making where strategies can adapt to change Democratic decision-making, especially the use of common resources	Policy makers and community leaders who can facilitate democratic processes
Accountability and participation	The ability to directly participate in decision-making	The lack of transparency and clarity in on-going processes of decision-making	Encourage local constituents to join in decision-making processes Policy makers to invest themselves in the well-being of local communities	Locally embedded and trusted representatives

The Netherlands as a green(er) society

First and foremost, we observed that there was collective desire to work towards establishing what has been termed “a green(er) society”. Although the game was introduced in the context of the SPES project, which may have prompted the players to think about sustainability as a key component of the game, the participants were nonetheless instructed to collectively construct a society as they wished. Most players in our sessions strongly expressed a desire to actualize a green and sustainable society in which they have a voice in how it is carried out. Once they were informed that the game would come to an end when the session exceeded the maximum number of externalities (this was set at 50 points to mimic societal entropy), the players started to actively conceive of plans that could prevent their societies from reaching the state of environmental and societal collapse. It was explicitly expressed by the players that the only way to *win* the game was to be able to keep playing the game, which was likened to how things play out in the real world.

Participants consistently framed sustainability transitions as deeply social and democratic processes rather than purely technical ones. Three overarching questions emerged: How can collective wellbeing be prioritized over individual gain? What forms of governance are needed to coordinate sustainable choices? How can societies navigate uncertainty while maintaining fairness and trust? Players imagined futures centred on circular economies, low-impact infrastructures, and strong community institutions such as food banks, community centres, and educational facilities. They resisted short-term fixes or non-sustainable options—even when these increased individual benefits—and preferred solutions that aligned with long-term collective goals.

Key tensions also surfaced. Participants struggled to balance environmental objectives with economic and social pressures, especially when external “events” introduced shocks or resource scarcity. They repeatedly highlighted the challenges of addressing accumulated externalities and systemic constraints with limited technical knowledge. A second tension concerned governance: players contrasted the transparent, participatory nature of the game with real-world policymaking, which they frequently described as opaque or inaccessible. This pointed to a perceived gap between citizens’ willingness to engage and the structures available for meaningful participation. Finally, the sessions revealed a tension between local agency and broader systemic forces, where individual or community initiatives alone were seen as insufficient without supportive governance and shared indicators of progress.

The centrality of public, low-impact infrastructure

In the pursuit of creating a liveable and sustainable society, there were several values that came up as a non-negotiable requirement. For instance, the players showed resistance towards non-sustainable policies, eventually refusing public intervention if they considered it to be in misalignment with their idea of a healthy and sustainable solution. This is evident in how the players refused to establish a bus route in their community after their failed attempt at creating a train station because the bus was not electric. Of course, this preference towards electric powered public transportation is most likely informed by Amsterdam’s clean air policy that incentivizes and prioritizes means of transportation that emit less harmful emissions. It was observed that when policies are shaped by and are responsive to the community’s actual concerns and interests, they tend to be replicated in imagined scenarios of a better future.

There was a strong preference towards establishing communal and public infrastructure which is managed locally. When plans to establish public infrastructure were set in motion (i.e. bridges, schools, research institutions, and community centres), it was common for there to be open discussion about the definition of public infrastructure and whether it should be publicly funded. Instead of allowing an individual to profit off public infrastructure, there was always a form of

negotiation that ensued: in exchange for public subsidization of operational costs, it was commonly agreed that infrastructure would remain free for the public to utilize.

People's welfare and the circular economy

Other social values were also deemed as a critical component to facilitate the transition towards realizing a sustainable future. Social values such as people's wellbeing, accessibility to social welfare, and the regulation of wealth were simultaneously tackled alongside issues of environmental destruction. This can be seen in the way players created a food bank in the city to make it accessible to as many people as possible and prioritizing the maintenance of public spaces. There were also instances in which laws were passed to redistribute wealth between the poorest and the richest members of society. These initiatives were rarely met with resistance when the objective of such policies was made clear and logical.

While players found it easier to devise plans that could minimize additional forms of pollution by proposing solutions based off circular economy principles (e.g. composting, alternative sustainable energy sources, and other known methods to minimize or repurpose waste), ideating on how to get rid of pollution that already existed in society proved to be difficult. For instance, numerous players proposed composting facilities that could repurpose agricultural and industrial waste to generate energy, which was envisioned to be an effective solution to both minimize unnecessary waste while maximizing energy production. However, no session was able to successfully conceive of an effective plan to tackle the externalities/pollution that had already been produced. There obviously were attempts: two out of the four sessions brought up the idea of sending the waste to space so that they would not have to carry the burden of waste removal. However, players were never completely satisfied with these short-term solutions.

Knowledge is key

The most common sentiment that was shared amongst the players was the need for more knowledge, expertise, and information to devise effective plans that do not rely on short-term solutions. Whenever the players recognized the difficulty of problem-solving on their own, they often opted to create research and educational facilities that could facilitate and fast track the production of solutions in a more scientific and technical manner. Players consistently tried to get rid of their externalities, but their failure highlights the real or perceived lack of information about trusted techniques to get rid of pollution and other kinds of economic externalities in a satisfying way.

Sustainability as a democratic and social challenge

The perspectives that emerged across the four Amsterdam workshops resonate strongly with broader sustainability debates in the Netherlands. Participants' focus on circularity, low-impact infrastructure, and community-managed resources mirrors national policy struggles around agriculture, energy, and land use—particularly in a country grappling with nitrogen emissions, water scarcity, and contestation over large-scale infrastructures like data centres. Yet, while Dutch policy frameworks emphasize technological innovation and sector-based transition pathways (as well as economic development), participants consistently reframed sustainability as a democratic and social challenge. Their emphasis on transparency, trust, and shared decision-making reflects a wider national concern about the perceived opacity of institutions, visible in debates over the nitrogen crisis, energy transitions, and local protests against hyperscale data centres. The games revealed that citizens are eager to engage but often feel excluded from the governance of

transitions that profoundly affect their lives and environments. The findings also speak directly to the Agenda 2030 areas of action and the five pillars of the SPES framework of sustainable human development (see Section 6).

Participation and empowerment emerged as foundational aspects. Players repeatedly stressed that meaningful sustainability transitions require accessible information, transparent processes, and trusted intermediaries who can facilitate public reasoning. Their imaginative societies relied on democratic coordination rather than top-down mandates, highlighting how empowered communities can identify fair and acceptable trade-offs.

Productivity surfaced through repeated investment in research centres, composting technologies, and circular systems. Participants recognized that innovation is necessary but insisted that it must be socially grounded, locally beneficial, and aligned with long-term ecological goals.

Equity was central to many decisions, from wealth-redistribution laws to the creation of food banks and social kitchens. Participants viewed fairness not as an add-on but as a prerequisite for social stability and collective action—an insight directly relevant to current Dutch tensions between rural and urban regions and the uneven distribution of transition costs.

Environmental sustainability was a constant concern, particularly when dealing with accumulated pollution. The difficulty participants experienced in the game when it came to eliminating existing, accumulated externalities, reflects broader national and EU challenges in addressing historical environmental burdens, despite strong commitments to circularity and emissions reduction.

Ambitious but grounded policy ideas

Overall, the Dutch workshops illustrate that citizens' visions for sustainability are ambitious but grounded: they combine environmental protection with social justice, community cohesion, and democratic governance. They also show that when provided with transparent information and space for collective problem-solving, citizens articulate policy ideas that align closely with both national concerns and the ambitions of the SPES framework.

Clear policy ideas emerged. Participants emphasized the need for trustworthy mediators to facilitate dialogue, accessible and comprehensible metrics to quantify ecological impact, and investments in public spaces that support lifelong learning and community engagement. The game sessions also underscored that citizens are ready to participate constructively when provided with transparent information, shared decision-making structures, and opportunities to collectively deliberate trade-offs.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

LOCAL AND NATIONAL LEVEL

- Invest in participatory governance infrastructures. Participants stressed the importance of transparent, accessible, and skilled facilitation to support informed public dialogue. Municipal and national authorities should build mechanisms—such as citizen assemblies, neighbourhood forums, or participatory planning units—supported by trained mediators who can enable meaningful citizen input on sustainability policies.
- Expand community-based infrastructure for sustainability. Reflecting the strong preference for local, publicly accessible institutions, policymakers should prioritize funding for community centres, educational hubs, circular economy initiatives, and other infrastructures that encourage collective learning and sustainable everyday practices.

EUROPEAN LEVEL

- Develop shared, citizen-friendly indicators of environmental impact at the European level. Participants identified the lack of clear and trusted metrics as a major obstacle to informed decision-making.

5.2.4. Norway

At a general level, participants in the Norwegian workshops expressed aspirations for Norway to become a sustainable society – one that balances economic development and social welfare with environmental responsibility. This vision extended beyond national borders, as participants emphasized Norway’s responsibility to contribute globally to sustainability goals, aligning their ambitions with the broader objectives of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Before discussing the Norwegian results more in detail, Table 8 outlines the main themes that emerged from the workshops in Norway and how these were framed by the participants.

Table 8: Summary of findings in Norway

THEME	ASPIRATIONS OR COLLECTIVE GOALS	KEY CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS	POLICY PRIORITIES AND IDEAS
Welfare state	Maintain and strengthen the welfare model as a foundation for sustainability	Pressure on welfare financing Fear of erosion due to market logics and economic pressures	Fair taxation Redistribution Maintain public ownership of infrastructure Uphold welfare entitlements
Work-Life Balance	More time for family, community, and self-development	Overwork Stress Unsustainable consumption	Shorter workweeks (e.g. 4-day week) Promote time-rich over material-rich life models
Green transition and innovation	Fulfill climate goals in a socially fair way	Fear of social protest from regressive green policies Overreliance on fossil fuels	Investments in green innovation Just transition policies Regulate to ensure public benefit from tech innovation
Economic competitiveness vs. sustainability	Balance Norway’s global competitiveness with strong climate and welfare commitments	Global economic constraints Risk of falling behind in green innovation Too reliant on oil	Public–private partnerships Strategic state investment (e.g., carbon capture and storage, wind, battery) Learn from oil sector taxation
Tax and subsidy system	Fair and efficient system that supports equity and growth	Tensions between social justice and global competitiveness	Reform of tax/subsidy structures Carbon taxes with social compensation
Future of work & AI	Protect income security and meaningful work	Risk of widespread job loss due to automation Mismatch with workfare norms	Debate on universal basic income Explore hybrid welfare models Support for retraining/reskilling
Public debate and media framing	Informed, balanced debate on sustainability and welfare issues	Dominant narratives favour oil dependency and market value framing	Reform education for critical thinking Challenge media bias Support alternative narratives

THEME	ASPIRATIONS OR COLLECTIVE GOALS	KEY CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS	POLICY PRIORITIES AND IDEAS
Norway's global role	Ethical leadership in sustainability aligned with SDGs	Risk of global inaction; potential economic cost of leading alone	Strengthen global accountability mechanisms for business Take moral leadership despite risks
Democratic innovation	Evolve democracy to support deeper citizen involvement	Limits of electoral democracy Democratic fatigue	Citizens' assemblies Participatory processes in policymaking

Support for comprehensive welfare state

However, the most prominent and consistent aspiration across all three workshops was the preservation and strengthening of the Norwegian welfare state. Participants viewed this institutional framework not only as a national achievement, but also as the key vehicle through which both domestic and global sustainability goals could be realized. This perspective was especially evident in the game's opening deliberations, inspired by John Rawls' veil of ignorance (Rawls, 2005), where participants reflected on the kind of institutions they would choose without knowing their social position. There was broad support for a system that ensures basic material security, universal access to healthcare and education, and opportunities for individuals to thrive and contribute meaningfully to society.

More time and less consumption

While participants agreed that Norwegians enjoy a relatively high standard of living—and that modest redistribution could address remaining within country inequalities—an additional aspiration was to create a society that allowed for more free time for personal development, community engagement, and family life. Ideas such as a four-day work week or six-hour workdays were discussed as ways to enhance well-being while reducing overconsumption and environmental strain. The vision expressed was not one of increased material wealth, but of greater time wealth, aligning with post-growth or well-being economy imaginaries (Calisto Friant et al., 2025).

In line with this, participants expressed concern about the excessive consumption and resource waste associated with Norway's consumer society. Yet there was limited optimism about the feasibility of transitioning to degrowth or a circular economy, given citizens' attachment to material comfort and the perceived constraints imposed by Norway's integration in the global economy. The dominant concern remained how to maintain a competitive national economy to sustain the welfare state and reduce the emission of greenhouse gases. Across all workshops, participants prioritized investment and regulation to stimulate technological innovation, particularly innovations aimed at producing climate-efficient goods and services as well as increase the production of energy. While these priorities reflected a largely technology-driven economic realism, some participants also voiced concern that rising energy demand could outpace the transition, and that new clean energy sources might simply be added to—not replace—existing fossil fuels.

Social justice and economic competitiveness

This tension between social justice and economic competitiveness emerged clearly in discussions around taxation and subsidies. A central policy dilemma identified was how to design fiscal systems for citizens and businesses that are both socially fair and internationally competitive. In relation to citizens, a recurring concern was the future of work in the age of automation and AI.

Given the foundational Norwegian welfare principle that individuals should support themselves through work, participants saw large-scale job displacement as a profound challenge. One proposed solution—particularly emphasized in one workshop—was the introduction of Universal Basic Income (UBI) – an unconditional cash payment to citizens (see for example Hasdell, 2020). UBI was seen as a potential means to ensure income security while also freeing up time for unpaid contributions to care work, community life, and sustainable lifestyles. However, views on UBI diverged. For some, it represented a radical alternative to the workfare model; for others, it was a bureaucratically efficient tool to simplify support for those outside employment. Participants also debated whether UBI would be financially feasible within Norway’s existing tax system, or whether it should be prioritized over other welfare obligations.

Role of the private sector

Regarding the private sector, discussions focused on how the state could effectively support innovation for sustainable economic growth without compromising the fiscal foundations of the welfare state. Participants debated whether it was realistic for the government to make large-scale investments in high-risk technologies—such as floating wind turbines, carbon capture and storage (CCS), and energy-intensive battery production—and whether such investments would yield public returns. While many agreed that the Norwegian state, with its strong financial resources, should play a role, there was a shared view that public investment should be paired with regulated public–private partnerships. Several participants pointed to historical policy instruments such as the “hjemfallsrett”- a legal principle in Norway that ensures hydropower resources revert to public ownership after a fixed period, safeguarding national control over critical energy infrastructure and natural resources (see Rheinstein and Glendon, 2025) - and the state’s tax regime for the oil sector, as models for ensuring public benefit from private sector collaboration. Others raised concerns about national security risks when critical infrastructure is not publicly owned.

Norway as a global actor

Participants also reflected on Norway’s role in the global context, both in terms of its historical contribution to climate change and its capacity to influence global sustainability efforts, given its wealth and strong institutions. There was discussion of how accountability mechanisms could be strengthened to ensure that Norwegian businesses adhered to sustainability standards not only domestically, but also across global value chains. While participants recognized the growing global collective action problem, exacerbated by major powers' reluctance to invest ambitiously in climate policy, they maintained that Norway, as a wealthy and influential state, should strive to demonstrate leadership in the face of geopolitical uncertainty. In this regard another rationale for global leadership and the need for Norway to engage in international and regional cooperation was the recognition that sustainability, security, and resilience cannot be achieved in isolation.

‘If we don’t build our own security, we have no security – we must form alliances. Even if we talk about starting from scratch, we still won’t be able to manage alone in the future’ (Participant in workshop 2, Norway).

Another major theme that emerged was the role and configuration of democracy and public discourse in shaping sustainability transitions. While participants generally expressed confidence in the functioning of Norwegian democracy—especially compared to concerns raised in other countries—they were critical of the role of mass and social media in shaping public debate. On one hand, dominant narratives about oil policy were seen as narrow, emphasizing the cleanliness of Norwegian oil production and its financial contribution to the welfare state. On the other hand, some participants argued that public sector services are often portrayed in the media and politics

as costs rather than as generators of societal value. This, they argued, reflects a narrow economic lens that undermines broader visions of well-being.

Education and more citizen participation in policymaking

Related to this, there were discussions about the need to reform education—not just to improve critical thinking, but to promote shared values that support collective action beyond economic growth. Enhancing community resilience in the face of increasingly frequent extreme weather events was also a concern. One workshop experimented with institutionalizing citizens' assemblies as a democratic innovation to complement electoral democracy. Citizens' assemblies are deliberative democratic bodies composed of randomly selected citizens who reflect the diversity of the population and are tasked with discussing and recommending solutions to complex political issues—offering an alternative or complement to electoral democracy (Van Reybrouck, 2018; Van Reybrouck et al., 2014). These were envisioned as tools to foster broader participation at local, national, and even global levels—both to generate ideas and foster ownership of climate-related policy decisions. This reflects a broader aspiration for the further evolution of organized democracy, in line with emerging thinking around deliberative democracy and citizen engagement.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

LOCAL AND NATIONAL LEVEL

- The goal of a sustainable society rests on the preservation of a comprehensive welfare state. There is room for changes to specific welfare policies but its core principles – such as universalism, equality, full employment, and a comprehensive social safety net – should be maintained.
- There is room for stricter environmental regulations on consumer products, for instance, requiring manufacturers to produce spare parts and provide repair options to reduce waste and extend product lifespans.
- Workshop discussions revealed an interest in democratic experimentation. For instance, citizen panels were highlighted as a promising tool to strengthen the legitimacy of decisions through public deliberation. Such instruments could also foster a broader understanding among citizens of complex issues like sustainability transitions.

GLOBAL LEVEL

- Participants were concerned about the reciprocity of national climate action. Individual or national climate mitigation efforts must be met with coordinated policy change at the global level. Citizens are likely to lose motivation for individual climate action if domestic emission cuts are offset by rising emissions elsewhere.

6. A comparative perspective on sustainable human development

In this section we move from a presentation of the empirical findings in the individual country cases to thinking about global and cross-country similarities and differences and how these relate to the five pillars of the SPES project's model of sustainable human development. The SPES project vision and framework are developed and explained in Biggeri et al. (2023). The pillars of the SPES framework are the objectives of equity, productivity, environmental sustainability, participation and empowerment, and human security. These are, in turn, aligned with people, prosperity, planet, partnership and peace, which are the five Ps, or areas of action, of the UN's Agenda 2030 for sustainable development (United Nations, 2015). Together with the findings presented in Section 0 above, the analysis and reflections offered below contribute – by providing a broad panorama of citizens' perspectives from across the globe – to the requested 'in-depth discussion on [...] pillars [of the sustainable human development paradigm, its] driving actors and triggering factors' (Biggeri et al., 2025: 24).

Before addressing the findings in relation to each of the five pillars separately, it should be noted that a general observation from the research activities is that these five dimensions appeared in the workshops and interviews as highly entangled and not easily separable categories. Gameplay and group discussions often centred precisely on interactions across the five Ps or across the SPES framework pillars and particularly on the reasons why it is so difficult to achieve desired outcomes in several domains at the same time. Conceptually, these tensions are linked to what Mandelli (2022) refer to as the eco-social growth trilemma. As reflected in the presentation of country results, each of the themes that emerged in the six countries typically cut across two or more of the five areas of action and corresponding pillars of the SPES framework. For instance, equity issues were often problematized not only in relation to people but also partnership and prosperity.

Not surprisingly, but important to highlight nevertheless, the workshops and individual interviews confirmed that the vision of sustainability is an uncontroversial and shared objective across Europe and the Global South. In other words, our research findings confirm that the goal of sustainability as a desired outcome can be described as universal. Nonetheless, when assessed through a cross-country comparative lens, it was evident that contextual factors like the level of social and economic development and geographic characteristics of the countries shaped the participants' perspectives and concerns.

6.1. Equity

In the SPES framework equity is about the objective to ensure 'equitable access to economic, political, social and cultural opportunities for all' (Biggeri et al., 2023: 31). This objective was recurrent in all countries but with slightly different emphases and expressions. At the general level, there appears to be a consensus around the view that a reduction of economic, social and political disparities is a central part of the sustainability agenda. Where the Global South and Europe differ notably is in the stronger attention to basic needs satisfaction and survival in the former than in the latter. Particularly Kenya and Pakistan have large informal economies and poorly developed social safety nets, making the consequences of poverty even more acute. In Kenya, for instance, this was also reflected in a strong focus on income-generating activities in the game since the players felt they had to provide economic and social security for themselves and their families in the absence of an adequate collective system. The focus on individual income and wealth accumulation, which they interpreted as individualistic, appeared to come at the expense of efforts to think about the community and society as a whole.

In Europe, the issues raised connected to equity, were directed more towards the institutional and systemic level, with reflections about the relationship between social inclusion, welfare, and a fair transition on the one hand, and environmental sustainability, on the other. In Europe, under the equity pillar, we can also highlight an attention to differences in, for instance, political participation and a desire for more inclusive policies. The concern that transition efforts had to be fair and should not burden the most vulnerable was articulated more explicitly in the European countries.

In addition, we found some acknowledgement and discussion of the global dimension of equity, connected to a recognition that rich countries were more responsible for climate change. However, this dimension emerged more strongly in some countries than others, with Sri Lanka and Norway being the cases in which this perspective was most prominent.

6.2. Productivity

The objective of productivity refers in the SPES vision of sustainable human development to '[t]he efficient use of economic, human and natural resources for the provision of goods and services, expanding human capabilities and increasing the standards of living for all' (Biggeri et al., 2023: 29). This objective resonates with the call for effective transition policies that emerged in several of the discussions in both Europe and the Global South. Some participants also suggested that the achievement of sustainability presupposed a new economic model, less focused on material consumption. The role of time appeared central to this discourse. The shift away from consumption should lead to more time think about the implications of individual actions (Sri Lanka), more time for other activities than work, such as spending time outdoors (Italy), have more time for community and family (Norway), or time to engage in the circular economy, seen as a people-to-people exchange with leisure and cooperative elements in it (Netherlands)

Another common theme was the tension between productivity, economic competitiveness, and economically profitable choices, on the one hand, and environmental harm and environmental objectives, on the other, although the contrast was arguably sharper in the Global South. These conflicting objectives connect also to the issue of individual need versus collective interests and responsibility, which was a recurrent issue in several countries in the Global South and Europe. The acceptability of choices that prioritised economic growth even if it came with a cost to the environment appeared greater in the Global South. This inclination was linked to the need to

address poverty, a large informal economy and individuals' existential needs such as securing a livelihood.

6.3. Environmental sustainability

In the context of sustainable human development, environmental sustainability points to '[t]he practice of responsibly managing and preserving natural resources and ecosystems, ensuring a balance between current and future well-being' (Biggeri et al., 2023: 32). This was another universally embraced objective across the European countries and the Global South. In poor as well as rich countries a 'healthy' natural environment is something people value and desire. In both Europe and the Global South environmental sustainability was framed as a collective action problem and more education about climate change and sustainability was highlighted as a precondition or potential facilitator for change.

There were also some notable nuances in issues related to environmental sustainability and the solutions to drive the transition forward. The lack of knowledge and awareness about climate change in the general population appeared particularly acute in the Global South countries and was emphasized as a fundamental barrier against change towards more sustainable practices. As highlighted also above, shortcomings in the social and economic dimensions were considered as an obstacle to green policy choices and environmentally conscious individual behaviour. Lack of jobs in the formal economy and poorly developed social protection systems were relevant factors in this regard.

Issues related to governance were raised in the Global South as well as in Europe, but weak coordination and problems of implementation and enforcement of regulations emerged as more significant challenges in the Global South countries, particularly Kenya and Sri Lanka. Examples of reasons identified by the participants, were clientelism and power asymmetries in the bureaucracy with environmental agencies being relatively weak. Furthermore, actions are often more reactive and crisis-driven than based on long-term planning and implementation of adaptation strategies. In contrast, in Europe discussions centred more on long-term visions and the potential to shift to an alternative societal model less focused on material consumption. Nevertheless, also in Europe there appeared to be considerable doubt whether it was realistic to achieve a transition away from conventional economic thinking and behaviour and into alternative models (e.g., the circular economy, publicly-owned and community-controlled infrastructure in the Netherlands), to the benefit of ecological sustainability.

6.4. Participation and empowerment

The terms participation and empowerment address the goal of "enabling individuals and communities to be active agents of their own future by ensuring a level playing field for the societal engagement of citizens and stakeholders" (Biggeri et al., 2023: 35). Looking at across the seven country cases included in this study, the discussions related to empowerment and participation centred primarily on the need to improve opportunities for citizen involvement and voice in political processes that make decisions about policy which directly affects citizens. There is a call for greater ownership to processes and policy output.

An interviewee in Kenya described nicely what participation and empowerment are about in the context of creating a sustainable and equitable society. It is

‘where [members] are involved in what is going on, having a voice in the development and the ongoings in the community. Not just be passive consumers or onlookers but involved in the affairs of their community and society’ (female, NGO representative, Kenya).

As levers to change individual behaviour, but also give citizens the tools they need to take an active part in shaping the sustainability transition and have real ownership of policy processes that affect them, there was a strong emphasis on knowledge and education in both the Global South countries and in Europe. Essentially, access to information and knowledge are crucial stepping stones in the promotion of people’s empowerment over sustainability transitions.

While shortcomings in basic political representation were highlighted as a challenge to the empowerment of communities and citizens in the Global South, an attention to democratic innovation, for instance, through the use of citizen assemblies and other deliberative tools, was more prominent in Europe.

6.5. Human security

The pillar of human security in the SPES framework means “[t]he sum of capabilities “freedom from want, freedom from fear, and freedom to live with dignity” (Biggeri et al., 2023: 37). Since this definition appears rather abstract, we try to unpack it by asking how we can frame the idea of human security based on the empirical findings from the country cases. The first observation to make is that except for Norway, discussions about peace, violent conflicts or war were largely absent. Rather it seems reasonable to suggest that human security in this context links with provisions of social, economic and environmental security, which can be seen as stabilising factors to avoid physical conflicts. Food and energy security would be part of this aspect. In addition, we would be inclined to see them as preconditions for the three freedoms listed as part of the above definition of human security.

Based on this widened interpretation of the notion of human security, it is relevant that Europe and the Global South shared a concern with risk protection, including social, economic and health risks as well as climate and other physical risks, suggesting also a tight interconnectedness of these dimensions in the pursuit of sustainability in very different countries. Thus, there was an emphasis on securing livelihoods and incomes, health and climate resilience.

An important difference was in the strategies citizens identified to handle threats to human risks. In the Global South efforts focused on handling immediate challenges to human security, like climate change and poverty. In Europe the debate typically centred on a perceived need to improve matters at a systemic and institutional level, e.g., by improving and expanding existing social protection systems. Norway was the only country where workshop participants raised and spoke in some detail about the issue of geopolitical tensions and reflected on potential consequences in terms of national security. In the Netherlands, the idea of “fighting against nature” emerged as an important dimension of human security, reflecting the country’s history of sea-related threats to land and its long-standing efforts to hold back the water.

7. Conclusions and policy recommendations

In this study we set out to explore citizens' aspirations, challenges and imagined solutions when faced with the need to advance the sustainability transition as part of global, regional, national and local policy agendas. We did so, examining a set of seven countries which face highly diverse social, economic, geographic and physical conditions. Against this background, it comes as no surprise that some of the perspectives and themes which emerged, differed across a Global South-Europe axis. For instance, an emphasis on economic development and the improvement of material living standards was more pronounced in the Global South countries, while the issue of overconsumption featured more prominently in the European countries.

Nonetheless, it is also striking how several aspirations were shared across these widely different contexts. The satisfaction of basic needs and a reduction of social inequalities stood out as defining features of sustainable human development and could not be traded away in efforts to foster more ecologically sustainable practices. Citizen participation and empowerment appeared as a perceived shortcoming of policies for sustainability in Europe as well as in the Global South countries. Overall, even if there was widespread recognition of the importance of reducing the ecological footprint and pressures on the environment from human activities, it remained a conundrum how to get decision-makers and citizens to move towards less profit-centred individual and collective decisions that weigh less on the environment.

Thus, we conclude with seven simple policy-oriented take-home messages that relevant to the national contexts as well as at the European level and in other global regions.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

1

Social inequalities hinder sustainable futures and must be addressed as part of the sustainability agenda. This includes the expansion of social safety net and social protection systems in the Global South and a careful attention to calls for a just transition and social inequalities in the consequences of transition policies in Europe.

2

Global climate justice is crucial for countries in the Global South. It is imperative to support governments in the Global South as they deal with the effects of climate change. Moreover, discourses about climate mitigation appears meaningless to citizens in the Global South if other nations continue with very high levels of greenhouse gas emissions.

3

There is a need for more **knowledge and education** about climate change and the importance of climate action. Investments in education about climate change and sustainability are needed at all levels to support and facilitate change.

4

Climate change and **sustainability discourses** must be carefully tailored to a variety of audiences. Particularly peripheral rural communities far away from the centres of political power do not understand and do not engage with elite discourses on climate action and sustainability. They should be met in a familiar language and with local examples that resonate with their everyday lives.

5

Better **coordination and integration of policy** that balance environmental, social and economic goals, are needed in all countries. Fragmented and siloed sectoral policies that do not add up to a coherent and holistic approach, are perceived as a challenge to progress towards sustainability in Europe as well as the Global South. Future efforts should concentrate on identifying best practices and there should be mechanisms in place for cross-national policy learning in Europe and globally. Shortcomings in implementation and enforcement of regulations are particularly pressing in the Global South.

6

Successful policy processes require ownership and **citizen involvement**. Improving opportunities for citizens to participate in policy processes will enhance legitimacy and ensure a better integration of local needs, which is important to prevent popular backlashes.

7

At the European and global level there is a need to develop **citizen-friendly indicators** of environmental impact and sustainability. The lack of metrics which citizens trust and understand, represents a barrier to informed opinions and decisions. The EU could lead by harmonizing sustainability indicators, making them transparent, comparable, and understandable for citizens and local governments. This would strengthen democratic oversight of sustainability transitions and improve trust in policy interventions.

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